

D 7.6

Overview of States' practice of HRJs including findings in three thematic WPs.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19878025](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19878025)

Authors

Name	Institution	Contact
Lead author: Maria Grahn-Farley. Lead WP1 & 2	University of Gothenburg	Maria.Grahn-Farley@law.gu.se
Shun-Ling Chen Co-lead WP4	Academic Sinica	shunlingchen@as.edu.tw
Ching-Yun Tai	Academic Sinica	chingyuntai129@gmail.com
Ya-Wen Yang	Academic Sinica	ywyang@gate.sinica.edu.tw
Yu-Ling Huang	National Cheng Kung University	yuling13905@gmail.com
Hsun-Hui Tseng	National Cheng Kung University	hsunhui@gmail.com
Hui-Chieh Su	National Taiwan University	huichieh@gmail.com
Haidar Al-Amirtaha	University of Gothenburg	haidaramirtaha@gmail.com
Mikael Baaz	University of Gothenburg	mikael.baaz@law.gu.se
Olga Bulgakova	University of Gothenburg	olgabulgakova199@gmail.com
Olena Chernenko	University of Gothenburg	olena.dotsenko@yahoo.com
Maria Nääv	University of Gothenburg	naav.maria@gmail.com
Anna Wallerman Ghavanini	University of Gothenburg	anna.ghavanini@law.gu.se
Swarup Sarkar	University of Gothenburg	swarup.sarkar@gu.se
Martin Westlund	University of Gothenburg	martin.westlund@law.gu.se
Sari Kouvo	University of Gothenburg	sari.kouvo@law.gu.se
Tuomas Ojanen Co-lead WP4	University of Helsinki	tuomas.ojanen@helsinki.fi
Milka Sormunen	University of Helsinki	milka.sormunen@helsinki.fi
Laura Carlson Lead WP5	University of Stockholm	Laura.Carlson@juridicum.su.se

Elica Ghavidel Rostami Olofsson	University of Stockholm	elica.ghavidel-rostami@juridicum.su.se
Paul Lappalainen	University of Stockholm	paul.lappalainen@gmail.com
Chiara Tea Antoniazzi	University of Trento	chiara.antoniazzi.2@unitn.it
Elena Fasoli Lead WP6	University of Trento	elenacristina.fasoli@unitn.it
Caterina Milo	University of Trento	caterina.milo@unitn.it
Paolo Turrini	University of Trento	paolo.turrini@unitn.it
Naina Kapur	Naina Kapur Law	naina.kapur@gmail.com
Namita Wahi	Namita Wahi and Associates	namita.wahi11@gmail.com
Jane Riley	English Language Editing, composition and design	janeriley@btinternet.com

Project	HR Just
Project Name	Human Rights Justifications
Document Name	D 7.6 Overview of States' practice of HRJs including findings in three thematic WPs.
GA. No:	101094346
Program	Horizon-CL2-2022-Democracy-01
Top	Topic: Horizon-CL@-2022-Democracy-01-09
Instrument	Research and Innovations Action (RIA)
Start	01.03.2023
Duration	39 months
Work Package	WP7
Associated Task	T7
Work Package	WP2
Task	T8
Submission date	29 April 2026
Lead	Maria Grahn-Farley
Department	UGOT
Email	Maria.grahn-farley@law.gu.se
Abstract	The term "Human Rights Justifications" (HRJs) was created for this project (HRJust), to describe occasions when human rights are used by the State as a tool of governance, rather than for the purpose for which they were originally created: as a protection for the individual against the power of the State. HRJs turn the human rights regime itself from being a regime holding the State

	accountable on behalf of the individual rights-holding subject, to being an instrument of governance on behalf of the State. The emergence and growth of HRJs is possible, in part, due to the unresolved relationship between the multilateral and the multipolar World Orders: whilst HRJs spring from the multilateral human rights regime, the scope for the State to use human rights in this way derives in part from the multipolar World Order.
Keywords	Human Rights Justifications (HRJs), Covid, Migration, Climate, Sweden, Finland, Taiwan, Ukraine, India. Multilateralism, Multipolarity.

Overview of States’ practice of Human Rights Justifications (HRJs), including findings from three thematic WPs

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
INTRODUCTION	10
DEFINITIONS.....	13
TOPICS OF INVESTIGATION	16
METHOD AND DESCRIPTION OF WORKFLOW	16
PLACE-BASED APPROACH FOR IDENTIFYING A HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATION (HRJ).....	17
A VALUE-BASED REALISM AND A DIGNIFIED FOREIGN POLICY	18
COLLABORATION BASED ON EQUALITY AND RESPECT	22
HORIZONTAL AND VERTICAL HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS	23
HORIZONTAL INTER-STATE USE OF HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS (HRJS)	24
THE UNIVERSAL PERIODIC REVIEW AND THE POLITICS OF HRJS	25
RUSSIA’S USE OF HRJ IN DEFENSE OF ITS INVASION OF UKRAINE	30
INDIA’S USE OF HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATION-LIKE ARGUMENTS (“RELATED NOTIONS”) UNDER GENERAL AGREEMENT ON TARIFFS AND TRADE (GATT).....	33
EU AND THE WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (WHO)	34
VERTICAL INTRA-STATE USE OF HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS (HRJS), WITHIN COUNTRIES AND ACROSS TOPICS.....	36
HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS AS A WAY TO BUILD INTERDEPENDENCY AND A FOUNDATION BASED ON SHARED VALUES: THE UKRAINE EXAMPLE.....	44

HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS BY TOPIC	51
COVID-19: THREE COUNTRIES AND THREE STRATEGIES	51
<i>Taiwan: Zero-COVID</i>	52
INDIA AND THE USE OF HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATION AND THE RIGHT TO DEVELOPMENT, A SEGWAY TO CLIMATE	55
CLIMATE LITIGATION AND THE USE OF “RELATED NOTIONS”.....	56
THE MIGRANT – THE NEW COLORLINE.....	59
CRISIS AND ITS PHASES.....	61
FUNCTION CREEP	63
ABSTRACT AND CONCRETE HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS.....	64
CONSTITUTIONAL DESIGN MATTERS	65
INDIA	67
SWEDEN	70
FINLAND.....	71
CONSTITUTIONAL DESIGN DEPENDENT ON TOPIC: CLIMATE CHANGE	71
CONSTITUTIONAL DESIGN DEPENDENT ON TOPIC: PANDEMIC PREPAREDNESS.....	72
THE ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY AND HUMAN RIGHTS DEFENDERS IN UPHOLDING MULTILATERALISM AND HOLDING THE GOVERNMENT ACCOUNTABLE WHEN USING HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS	73
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AS A CORE COMPONENT OF EPIDEMIC RESPONSE: A PUBLIC HEALTH PERSPECTIVE	74
A MODEL DEVELOPED BY HRJUST FOR HOW TO REINVIGORATE CIVIL SOCIETY - RINGS ON WATER (ROW) THROUGH DEMOCRATIC INCLUSION	74
WHEN HUMAN RIGHTS DEFENDERS ARE TARGETED: A GAP IN EU HORIZON REPORTING SYSTEM	75
THE CONNECTION BETWEEN A GEOPOLITICAL AND A MUNICIPAL POLITICAL CONTEXT	78
UKRAINE.....	79
TAIWAN	82
INDIA	84
FINLAND.....	85
SWEDEN.....	85
WHAT ROLE GEOPOLITICS PLAYS IN STRATEGY, RESOURCES AND REACH	87
THE RAPIDLY CHANGING GEOPOLITICAL MAP – REASON TO REFLECT.....	89
THE GEOPOLITICAL EFFECTS ON TOPICS	93
MIGRATION.....	93
COVID-19	94
<i>Taiwan</i>	95
<i>Finland and Sweden</i>	96
“RIGHT TO DEVELOPMENT” AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	96
A VALUE-BASED REALISM MEETS HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS THROUGH EQUALITY AND INTERDEPENDENCY	99
RELATED NOTIONS.....	99

EU AND HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS	101
WHAT ROLE HAS EU IN COMPARISON BETWEEN INTERNAL TO EU AND EXTERNAL TO EU	102
COMPARING THE GENERAL AND THE PARTICULAR.....	103
EXAMINATION OF THE TOPICS OF INVESTIGATION	105
ARE HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS (HRJs) UNDERMINING THE CREDIBILITY AND LEGITIMACY OF THE HUMAN RIGHTS REGIME ITSELF?.....	105
ARE HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS BEING MORE LIKELY TO BE USED AT MOMENTS OF CRISIS?	106
ARE THERE SIGNIFICANT AND IMPORTANT GAPS IN HUMAN RIGHTS REGULATIONS?	107
IS THERE A LACK OF THEORETICAL UNDERSTANDING OF THE IMPLICATIONS AND UNCERTAINTIES ABOUT THE ROLE AND RESPONSE OF GLOBAL ACTORS LIKE EU WHEN STATES USE HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS?.....	107
RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER EXAMINATION	108
RECOMMENDATION 1: HORIZON AS A MULTILATERAL DIPLOMATIC INSTRUMENT.....	108
RECOMMENDATION 2: EDUCATE CIVIL SOCIETY TO BE OBSERVANT THAT IT IS AFTER THE IMMEDIATE CRISIS HAS PASSED THAT THE RISK OF FUNCTION CREEP IS HIGHER	109
RECOMMENDATION 3: TO EXPAND THE CAPACITY FOR HUMAN RIGHTS TO SERVE AS A COMPARATIVE MATRIX FOR CIVIL SOCIETY WHEN HOLDING THE STATE ACCOUNTABLE	109
RECOMMENDATION 4: TO REFORM THE HORIZON REPORTING SYSTEM TO PROTECT RESEARCHERS AND HUMAN RIGHTS DEFENDERS AT RISK.....	110

Overview of States’ practice of Human Rights Justifications (HRJs), including findings from three thematic WPs

“Europe is in a fight. A fight for a continent that is whole and at peace. For a free and independent Europe. A fight for our values and our democracies. A fight for our liberty and our ability to determine our destiny for ourselves. Make no mistake – this is a fight for our future.”

– 2025 State of the Union Address by President von der Leyen

Executive Summary

The term “Human Rights Justifications” (HRJs) was created for this project (HRJust), to describe occasions when human rights are used by the State as a tool of governance, rather than for the purpose for which they were originally created: as a protection for the individual against the power of the State. HRJs turn the human rights regime itself from being a regime holding the State accountable on behalf of the individual rights-holding subject, to being an instrument of governance on behalf of the State. The emergence and growth of HRJs is possible, in part, due to the unresolved relationship between the multilateral and the multipolar World Orders: whilst HRJs spring from the multilateral human rights regime, the scope for the State to use human rights in this way derives in part from the multipolar World Order.

Key Findings:

- 1) When multilateralism is in conflict with, or under threat from, multipolarity, human rights move from being a top-down (where there is an international objective norm) to bottom-up (where each right acquires its meaning from its local context) regime, with States seizing the initiative when international rules become local rules because a weakened unified international source to check such actions, enabling States to use human rights proactively as a tool of governance. Whilst this has new benefits and opportunities (the rules becoming more sensitive to place and historicity), it also generates new challenges because the existing system was designed to act as a means of protection of the individual against the State, and not as an instrument of governance.

- 2) That the existence of a liberal democratic state is indispensable to protecting human rights. If the liberal democratic state retreats from its responsibilities, Civil Society on its own cannot take on the role of advancing and protecting the individual through human rights.

- 3) That human rights are not only a value-based regime of rules and principles but also create comparative and common metrics between countries, and between Civil Society networks and organizations, that allow Civil Society to make comparisons between a variety of laws and regulations across jurisdictions and countries. A large part of Civil Society does not have, or finds it a challenge to acquire, the resources or skills required to evaluate the effects of proposed legislation that risks infringing individual human rights and therefore to provide effective critique, for example the effects of specific regulations and programs proposed by the State when regulating migrants. This is when human rights can serve as a comparative matrix and help Civil Society understand effects of one law in one country when the same law is being proposed in their own country.

- 4) When HRJs are used by the State to defend its own decisions, there should be a “heightened scrutiny” to make sure that HRJs are not used by the State to circumscribe its human rights and constitutional and municipal legal obligations towards individual person’s human rights, particularly those in already vulnerable or discriminated groups.

- 5) The migrant (in contrast to migration) is the new colorline: in the past, much discrimination was focused on ethnicity, as famously described by W.E.B. DuBois: “The problem of the Twentieth Century is the problem of the color line,” when writing about legacy of slavery and colonialism. Our research has identified that there is a shift to discrimination against anyone who is a migrant or has a migrant background, with HRJs used both to discriminate against and to infringe upon and limit the rights of these groups.

- 6) That once a HRJ has been both normalized and institutionalized, there is a risk of function creep, where the new infringement of a right will be used not only in the context of the original HRJ but for unrelated purposes. For example, HRJs (the fight against gangs) in Sweden were used to justify the adoption of critiqued Stop-and-search laws to be able to search mostly boys with migrant backgrounds - but the same law is now being used to protect the Israeli embassy after the Israeli and USA’s armed attack on Iran.

Introduction

“We simply cannot wait for this storm to pass. This summer showed us that there is simply no room or time for nostalgia. Battlelines for a new world order based on power are being drawn right now. So, yes, Europe must fight. For its place in a world in which many major powers are either ambivalent or openly hostile to Europe. A world of imperial ambitions

and imperial wars. A world in which dependencies are ruthlessly weaponised. And it is for all of these reasons that a new Europe must emerge.”

– 2025 State of the Union Address by President von der Leyen

The HRJust project was created and commenced against a backdrop of major global challenges and conflicts, including challenges to the established rights-based order, where previously international bodies and agreements provided the context for interactions between States, and between the State and the individual. Increasingly, there have been changes to the ways States relate to each other (moving from a unipolar multilateral rule-based order to a more multipolar – interest-based order), and how States relate to their populations (openly in national and local elections challenging the liberal democratic foundations) which affects many significant issues including the three selected for HRJust: States’ management of the COVID-19 pandemic, migration and climate change.

This context of change includes the expansion of support for far-right bodies within Europe, and which appeared to be threatening to undermine European stability, peace and unity. These factions were initially regarded as isolated extremists, whose threats could be managed and responded to by strengthening human rights and promoting a more inclusive society. However, it has become clear that it is not possible “educate” away far-right extremist views with the help of a focus on human rights and inclusion, and that support for these positions is to be found in several EU Member States.

We were also shaping our proposal at a time when Europe still had the 2015 refugee crisis fresh in its memory and the EU migrant compact was still being drafted. The focus then was on strengthening human rights and supporting the people working to defend them, rather than preventing migration to Europe altogether as seems now to be the goal, in large. As a result, the debate is now how to save the very existence and relevance of human rights as a regulatory regime in a multipolar World Order.

Even as the grant proposal for HRJust was being finalized in 2022, Russia began its full scale invasion of Ukraine, and the ongoing implications of this and other conflicts has made it

clear - not only to the team's researchers but also the EU - that a value-based rule of law order cannot be taken for granted on either the international or the municipal levels. Liberal democracy needs an active defense against authoritarianism. Further, we must also find new strategies and create new networks and alliances for this defense as the political context risks shifting towards a normalization of authoritarian models of governance rather than liberal democratic values. This can be seen very sharply when we consider the Swedish example: of the five countries being studied (Sweden, Finland, Ukraine, Taiwan and India), Sweden demonstrates perhaps the most unexpected example of a shift to normalization of an authoritarian approach to governance, and use of HRJs for this purpose.

A central part of our studies has been to map how human rights - in the form of HRJs - are being used in moments of crisis through place-based studies sampled from Sweden, Finland, Ukraine, Taiwan and India, focused on three significant but different issues, which also reflect three different timeframes:

The COVID-19 global pandemic, which reset the ideas of what is normal and acceptable democratic behavior of a State when it comes to surveillance of its people and restrictions of their movements. This project looks at the COVID-19 strategies in Taiwan, Finland and Sweden.

Migration: this has focused on migration issues in connection to Taiwan, Sweden and Ukraine. One of the most significant findings of the project is that the new colorline is drawn around the migrant, not the concept of migration itself, but rather focused on individual persons who are migrants or with migrant backgrounds but already residing within the national border of the receiving country.

Climate change is another global crisis which is having a massive impact on the enjoyment of human rights; and responses to such a crisis can also negatively affect human rights. Nonetheless, this project finds that States have mostly been cautious in recognizing this nexus or have in any case claimed a wide margin of maneuver, notwithstanding the flourishing of human rights-based climate litigation. Our work

includes a focus on India and the relationship between the Rights to Development and Climate-related litigations.

The need for understanding and clarity of how the relationship between multilateralism and multipolarity affects the individual human rights protection has become increasingly crucial as the project has progressed. The Russian invasion of Ukraine is ongoing with little sign of diminishing, and more recently there have been further armed conflicts, for instance in the Middle East, involving many countries including the US, Iran and Israel, with its implications spreading - for instance with Iran attacking US interests in other locations outside the immediate geography of the Middle East. Simultaneously, other tensions have developed into armed conflicts, such as between Pakistan and Afghanistan. Further, there are ongoing issues about other potential geopolitical pressures, such as the US's interest in Greenland, an island under the sovereignty of Denmark, and a NATO ally.

Definitions

“Human Rights” in this study mean positivist human rights – as adopted by States with the understanding that they generate legally binding obligations upon the State – this excludes natural law frameworks and morality-based understandings of human rights, in this Deliverable.

To allow for place-based analysis of Human Rights Justifications (HRJs), we decided to use a broad definition of a HRJ: when the State uses a positivist form of a human right in defense of its actions and/or decisions.

HRJs turn the human rights regime itself from being a regime holding the State accountable on behalf of the individual rights-holding subject, to becoming an instrument of governance on behalf of the State.

This Deliverable describes HRJs taking place on the international horizontal level (State to State), and the vertical municipal level (State to individual within countries) and refers the reader to more detailed analyses in designated reports. When it comes to the international

level, the “State” usually refers to a national government agency or department such as the state department or the government as the executive organ representing the State on the international stage. On the municipal level, in this deliverable the “State” generally refers to the legislator, the executive or the courts. We have noted the interactions between these elements of the State, which differs from country to country. For instance, in a Parliamentary system of government such as India, the legislature does not have much independence from the executive. In Sweden, there are only weak forms of ex-ante review. In addition, we have noted that the “State” can also be understood in its broadest meaning in its *e-contrario* – a non-private actor.

When using the terms “multilateralism” and “multipolarity” we use these concepts from the position of being a mostly law-based consortium, meaning that there is a heightened focus on the legal rules and norms governing human rights between States and through International Organizations and Institutions both on the international and the national levels. We utilise the term “multipolarity” mostly in its relation to multilateralism. Whereas “multilateralism” (simply put) is governed by rules and law, multipolarity is driven by power and interests. The project treats multipolarity as a descriptive fact, as something that exists and is possible to observe, rather than something that normatively is to be striven for.

This differs from, for example, how Chantal Mouffe in 2009 describes multipolarity as in itself a development that can bring a normative good and is also possible to control and shape¹. To Mouffe, multipolarity is an alternative to what she regards as a hegemonic multilateralism, where multilateralism and multipolarity stand in both opposition and competition to each other.

In contrast, Pierre Hassner in 2007 approached the relationship between multilateralism and multipolarity from the position that EU takes on the role of being a regional multipolar geographical actor while at the same time wanting to have a leading role as a world regulator through multilateralism. Hassner questions whether the distinction between

¹ Chantal Mouffe, Democracy in a Multipolar World, 37 Millenium: Journal of International Studies (2009), 549-561

multilateralism and multipolarity need to be redefined, not as oppositional concepts but rather to be understood as complementary and compatible concepts².

Despite their differences, both Hassner and Mouffe present a view on both multilateralism and multipolarity as concepts that it is possible for Europe to shape and reshape.

Like Hassner, Katie Verlin Laatikainen in 2012 does not see multilateralism and multipolarity as necessarily oppositional but rather as coexisting with one another. She makes a distinction between multilateralism **vs** multipolarity, on one hand, and multilateralism **and** multipolarity on the other³.

In our project, dominated as it is by lawyers and particularly human rights lawyers, our norms and rules are at the center of the analysis. This lends itself to have a focus on multilateralism and on how to understand a distinction between how rules (in the form of human rights) function in the nexus between multilateralism and a multipolar order. Legal scholars are not blind to the role of power, but most of us still believe that even power follows some rules. Within this context, the rule based multilateral order is unlikely to completely disappear, and it is not likely that, from an international law position, multipolarity will be driven only by power and not also be channeling and being constrained by rules generated within a multilateral system. Laatikainen in 2012 describes how “institutionalists” recognize the end of American hegemony but also believe that what will remain after American hegemony will be the multilateral institutions created during American hegemony⁴. And with these multilateral institutions, their values of equality and non-discrimination will still have some force upon the ways States in a multipolar world exercise their powers. Laatikainen means that differently from a multipolar realism - where

² Pierre Hassner, L'Union européenne face à la multipolarité et au multilatéralisme, 334, *Esprit* (2007), pp 55-56.

³ Katie Verlin Laatikainen, EU multilateralism in a multipolar world, *in* Routledge Handbook on the European Union and International Institutions, Routledge (1st ed., Knud Erik Jørgensen & Katie Verlin Laatikainen eds., 2012). 473.

⁴ Katie Verlin Laatikainen, EU multilateralism in a multipolar world, *in* Routledge Handbook on the European Union and International Institutions, Routledge (1st ed., Knud Erik Jørgensen & Katie Verlin Laatikainen eds., 2012). 474.

power is the organizing principle, the strength of the non-discrimination principle of multilateral institutionalism will make power alone unable to act unhindered.

The project is not assessing the EU as a unified block, but we are instead describing its divergent but indispensable role when it comes to supporting liberal democracy in both Taiwan and Ukraine, and where its role in this regard is less pronounced when it comes to India in human rights.

Topics of Investigation

The grant application presented a set of underpinning topics of investigations, presumptions and motivations for why this project is of importance and interest for the EU to fund. These presumptions and motivations are presented below. These topic of investigations and presumptions have guided our research and project development:

- 1) HRJs risk undermining the credibility and legitimacy of the human rights regime itself
- 2) HRJs are more likely to be used at moments of crisis
- 3) States' behaviors in this situation are not regulated by any international, regional or national regimes
- 4) There are significant and important gaps in human rights regulations and a lack of theoretical understanding of the implications and uncertainties about the role and response of global actors like EU when States use HRJs.

Method and Description of Workflow

The starting point for HRJust has been the legal method relying on the sources of law and the hierarchy of norms as they present within national legal systems and within international public law.

The evolution of a Human Rights Justification doctrine and its empirical application through a lens of gender and intersectionality is a common theme throughout the duration of this project.

By developing and testing the concept of “Human Rights Justification” (HRJ), since this is a terminology invented in the Grant Proposal for HRJust, we first had to empirically study what happens when the State uses human rights to justify its actions and decisions. We had the abstract definition of a HRJ to start with as defined above, namely when the State uses a positivist form of a human right in defense of its actions and/or decisions.

Our focus has been how to empirically test the legal analytical understanding of HRJs on the horizontal level and vertical level, to discern how the relationship between multilateralism and multipolarity influences the individual human rights protection.

Place-based Approach for Identifying a Human Rights Justification (HRJ)

The following diagram shows the place-based approach of identifying a HRJ. It begins with the action of the State, and the quality of the human right invoked (understood as legally binding upon the State invoking the right), and the purpose of the action.

A Value-Based Realism and a Dignified Foreign Policy

Human Rights Justifications (HRJs) exist within a multilateral paradigm taking place against the backdrop of an emerging World Order grounded in multipolarity and exhibiting signs of democratic backsliding.

Our project, with its focus on countries within the EU (Sweden and Finland) as well as outside of the EU such as India, Ukraine (European but not currently an EU Member State) and Taiwan, is founded on an idea of equality and respect regardless of geographical location, and on shared universal values of liberal democracy and the defense of multilateral collaboration. It is the nexus of a value-based interdependency between EU-members (Sweden and Finland) and third countries (Ukraine, Taiwan and India) that has generated a tentative map for how to protect a multilateral rule-based order founded on human rights at the moment of a weakened central institution such as the United Nations. This project will demonstrate how this interdependency might function in a transitional period when the relationship between multilateralism and multipolarity is taking shape.

The HRJ did not appear on its own in a vacuum. HRJs are themselves an outgrowth of a diversified State-dependent human rights norms regime, situated within the gap constructed out of the unclear relation between multilateralism and multipolarity. HRJs are in part made possible because there is insufficient clarity with respect to the relationship between a multilateral and a multipolar World Order. HRJs draw on the source of multilateralism (rule and rights-based inter-state World Order) but finds their practical expression through the ambiguities derived by a multipolar World Order where State interests and geopolitical considerations are what shapes how the State expresses human rights, where the link between the State's actions are link between and the international regulatory framework from where the rights originated has weakened.

A significant shift during the lifetime of this project is how the perception of human rights as part of the multilateral World Order has transformed from being generated from one epicenter (the UN in Geneva and New York City, supported by the USA as the hegemon) outwards, to what we, in this project, can see as an interdependency between the multilateral and multipolar orders, as a result of the absence of a strong external entity upholding one singular international human rights norm.

This shift has been made particularly clear by how the narrative of Ukraine has shifted throughout the lifespan of this project. At the beginning of the project, it was generally considered that it was the EU that helped Ukraine in its existential self-defense against the Russian full-scale invasion, but over the duration of this project, it has become clear that the situation of Ukraine raises many significant issues for Europe and Europe's defense of its own values. The war is not only about territory but also about the defense of identity, grounded in values such as human rights and liberal democracy. The position of Taiwan also raises issues: due to its status, Taiwan is unable to be a party to the international human rights treaties, so instead has developed a mechanism to enable it to participate by creating an interdependent relationship to human rights and multilateralism based on the shared values of human rights. In contrast, India has been a founding member of the UN and the international human rights regime and has been committed to liberal democracy and

human rights values since its independence from British colonial rule but is going through an internal political shift towards a greater nationalist and less multilateral position.

Some of the multipolar shifts and political realities that set the context for HRJs are neatly described by the Finnish President Alexander Stubb, who identifies the invasion of Ukraine as the moment when the post-Cold War unipolar United States hegemonic World Order ended and that we now are in a new era, not yet fully defined or understood. In this Deliverable, we will loosely follow Stubb's proposition of a **value-based realism**.⁵ He defines this broadly as "a set of universal values based on freedom, fundamental rights, and international rules, which take into account the realities of global diversity, culture, and history of the nation-states, regions, and continents that make up the global order of international relations⁶." Stubb pairs this value-based realism with what he defines as a "**dignified foreign policy**" which should be "grounded in mutual respect, where [Europe] lead by example and not extortion⁷."

The importance of EU's liberal democratic and human rights value-based position to non-EU Member States has been made clear by the Taiwanese and Ukrainian researchers. The role of the EU must expand from being the facilitator and the protector of liberal democracy to becoming a true and equal partner among like-minded peoples in a wider variety of settings and collaborating not only with States in maintaining and upholding a liberal and democratic rule and rights based multilateral regime governing the relations between States and its people. The need for and opportunities of such a path towards a "dignified foreign policy" is clear from the research originating from within Ukraine and Taiwan and perhaps to a lesser extent from within India as our research demonstrates that India relies on its constitution for its internal (vertical) use of rights, whereas Taiwan's Civil Society finds support in the international human rights community, and Ukraine relies on common identity with international and particularly EU values. At the core of these three nations' interactions with human rights and liberal democratic values is the importance of both a

⁵ Alexander Stubb, *The Triangle of Power*, (paperback) Columbia Global Report (2026), p 26

⁶ Alexander Stubb, *The Triangle of Power*, (paperback) Columbia Global Report (2026), pp 26-27.

⁷ Alexander Stubb, *The Triangle of Power*, (paperback) Columbia Global Report (2026), p 29.

value-based realism (that is able to take into account both the place of where the rights are to be applied and used and also the particular history of this place) and, even more strongly, the importance of a dignified interdependent foreign policy, often anchored to strong and active Civil Society communities relying on a shared value-base of freedom and equality both from international as well as municipal regulatory regimes.

The countries in our project, Sweden, Finland, Taiwan, India and Ukraine, have many significant differences, making a legal comparative study between them more complicated. For example, in a strict constitutional approach, such a comparison would have little practical use since their size, geopolitical situation and history varies too much for a legal comparison to be made following a strict comparative legal method. Instead, these countries' ways of maneuvering the relationship between a multilateral and multipolar World Order when it comes to human rights are of great importance at this moment in history just because they each demonstrate their own functional use of human rights, providing a useful spectrum of models of what is possible to do and what should be avoided if we are to maintain a rule-based multilateral human rights regime.

We have found - to paraphrase Leo Tolstoy's *Anna Karenina*, "Happy families are all alike, every unhappy family is unhappy in its own way," - that the same can be said about misuses and abuses of HRJs. It is relatively easy to imagine and design a regime for when the purpose and the aim is compliance with human rights, but it is far more difficult to describe a regime to counter the misuses and abuses of HRJs by States when human rights no longer regulate compliance but becomes instruments of governance.

To further paraphrase Tolstoy's observations about happy families: when the liberal democratic State's goal is to respect human rights, the human rights regime functions well to guide its decision-making and its HRJs will also have positive justifications and motivations - because the regime is structured for the "happy family".

However, the challenge is when the State, instead of seeing human rights as a regime to aspire towards and to be guided by, sees human rights as a hindrance to its goals or a roadblock to be navigated around. It is in this context, when the family is "unhappy" that

HRJs become counterproductive and the human rights regime has a difficulty in responding effectively to States' misuse of HRJs.

We have found that it is mostly the State's internal institutions and regulatory regimes such as constitutional design that determine how HRJs are being used and how they can be scrutinized and checked when in a condition of "unhappiness", (addressed in more detail below) i.e. how much scope the State has for its negative use of HRJs. This means that the relationship between the national constitutional framework and multilateralism in a multipolar World Order must be understood from a perspective of interdependency and not seen as mutually independent regimes when it comes to the protection of human rights. Knowledge and preparedness for how international and national human rights interact with each other, especially in a weakened multilateral system, against the backdrop of a multipolar World Order must be further developed.

Collaboration based on Equality and Respect

As an EU Horizon-funded project, HRJust is unusual or even unique in that our researchers from India (two beneficiaries) and Taiwan (three beneficiaries) are full and equal partners in the project. All of them are full and equal partners in the project, sharing the same rights and responsibilities as EU Member State-based beneficiaries. By including Taiwan colleagues as beneficiaries, including through Academia Sinica acting as a Work Package Lead, the project has gained unique and invaluable insights into what role the EU can play in the future, and its current opportunities for supporting a liberal democratic agenda in Taiwan. Due to the situation in their home country, our Ukrainian researchers are conducting their research out of the University of Gothenburg as fully funded researchers but still based within Kharkiv, Ukraine most of the time. The significance of this, i.e. to be fully equal within a project like a Horizon consortium should not be underestimated. These are the first steps towards what the Finnish President Stubb has envisaged as a "dignified foreign policy" (as referenced above). It was important for the project and its core idea of

equality and respect between EU Member State-based beneficiaries and Third Country beneficiaries, as it plays out in a Global South and East-West map. In this way, this project foreshadowed the usefulness with an approach based on a foreign policy of respectful interdependency between those States and peoples that share the same values of liberal democracy and human rights. This interdependency cannot stop at the State level but must also include those representatives of Civil Society, and academics in these countries that share those values, which the results from our project so clearly demonstrate.

Horizontal and Vertical Human Rights Justifications

The original version of Human Rights in the post-World War II era was constructed through international treaty law, as legally binding treaties between States. Through these treaties, States bound themselves to uphold a set of individual rights within their countries. If severe enough, a violation of an individual right within a country could be seen as a violation of that State's treaty obligations towards all the other States that also were parties to the same multinational treaties. As a result, Human Rights at the international level can often be seen as having legally weak instruments of enforcement, if there is no court connected to the treaty regime, with enforcement reliant on the collective of States themselves. But what multilateral human rights regimes lack in enforcement they might gain in flexibility. The challenges with a reformulated relationship between multilateralism and multipolarity is that the Human Rights regimes are based on a flexibility allowing the interest of the sovereign State to be taken into account, but it does not allow for a well fitted model for how to take multipolarity into account (where regional geopolitical interests that go beyond the internal national interests of the State influence the application of human rights both within the State and on the international arena). In other words, this flexibility has in part given rise to the creation of HRJs, because the individual State can argue that its interests - that of the sovereign State - from a bottom-up perspective determine the meaning of the international agreements to its own advantage. Thus, geopolitical considerations shape the behaviors of the individual sovereign State beyond the individual national sovereign interests. Therefore,

when considering how a body like EU can relate to States' use of HRJs it might be more of a question of a realignment between a multilateral rule-based regime and a multipolar realism.

If there is an appropriate court, then enforcement will lie with that Court, and its relationship with the individual violating State. In this Deliverable we have only focused on the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) because Sweden, Finland and Ukraine are subject to it and there is no Asian regional human rights court (which would otherwise have covered Taiwan and India). The legal question that is being addressed through a study of the ECHR case law is whether the distinction between HRJs and positive obligations can be methodologically and theoretically described. This will be addressed further below.

When HRJs take place within a country it is usually because there are mechanisms that have transformed the original horizontal relation between States and human rights, into a vertical relationship between the State and its citizens or other individuals living within the State, usually through incorporation or transformation. Most of our research connects to these municipal and often constitutional legal regimes and how they convert the horizontal regime of international human rights into a vertical regime regulated by national legislators and domestic courts. What we have found is that the constitutional design for how to bring human rights into the national legal system is of importance for understanding the effects on the individual human rights protection when the State uses HRJs to justify its actions and decisions.

Horizontal Inter-State use of Human Rights Justifications (HRJs)

The study and the examples herein, serve to illustrate how different States employ human rights as a flexible instrument to justify State actions or decisions in matters pertaining to human rights on the horizontal inter-State level.

The Universal Periodic Review and the politics of HRJs

This text is authored by Elica Ghavidel Rostami Olofsson, and the content and part of the text is taken from the report: HRJust Method Memo A4, Elica Ghavidel, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10455680

An illustrative study was conducted on States' use of HRJs within the framework of the Universal Periodic Review (UPR), with the aim of demonstrating how such justifications may be identified in State argumentation⁸. The empirical material of this study consists of examples drawn from national reports submitted by China, Finland, India, the Russian Federation, Sweden, Ukraine, and the United States⁹. We have included countries outside the five on which our project focuses, such as China, Russia and the United States because the way that the countries in our study react to human rights justification is often related to the geopolitical context such as being in geographic proximity or in other ways affected by these powerful nations.

⁸ HRJust Method Memo A4, Elica Ghavidel, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10455680

⁹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, available at: [G1825462.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023]; UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Finland*, 5 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/FIN/1, available at: [G2244387.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023]; UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023]; UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023]; UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Sweden*, 11 November 2019, A/HRC/WG.6/35/SWE/1, available at: [G1932124.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023]; UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023]; UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](#) [accessed 18 December 2023].

As demonstrated by the examples below, the study indicates that States employ HRJs in varied and context-dependent ways. In addition to clear and explicit instances of HRJs, States frequently integrate such justifications with other forms of argumentation, and in certain cases advance arguments that lack HRJs altogether.

Ukraine's national report, in its discussion of civil and political rights and the freedom of mass media, notes that the State has introduced a procedure for "banning international television channels, films, and printed materials that endanger the independence, sovereignty, or territorial integrity of Ukraine." The procedure further prohibits "the dissemination of war propaganda and the justification of the occupation of parts of Ukraine." In this context, the State invokes HRJs to legitimize the measure, asserting that it is "justified under Article 20 of the ICCPR and complies with the requirements set out in Article 19(3) of the ICCPR¹⁰."

In another example, in its discussion of economic, social and cultural rights, specifically in relation to women and health, the United States' national report appears to employ a combination of arguments based on State sovereignty and HRJs, albeit in a "reversed" manner. In this instance, HRJs are not invoked to expand or reinforce internationally recognized rights, but rather to contest their scope and interpretation. The report states:

"As the United States has noted on many occasions, there is no international human right to abortion, whether under that name or under other terms like 'sexual and reproductive health.' Rather, as President Trump has stated, 'our Nation proudly and strongly reaffirms our commitment to protect the precious gift of life at every stage, from conception until natural death.' The United States believes in the sovereign right of nations to make their own laws to protect the unborn and rejects any interpretation of international human rights to require any State to provide access to abortion. As President Trump has further stated,

¹⁰ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 18, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023).

‘Every person – the born and the unborn, the poor, the downcast, the disabled, the infirm, and the elderly – has inherent value’.¹¹

This example illustrates how HRJs may be combined with assertions of State sovereignty to justify policy positions, while simultaneously challenging prevailing interpretations of international human rights norms.

In relation to the intersection of human rights and the environment, India employs HRJs in combination with development-oriented arguments. In its 2022 national report, submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21, the Indian government repeatedly cites “development” as a justification for its actions in compliance and as well as its non-compliance with human rights. It emphasizes its commitment to “continue its efforts to improve the environment and address climate change,” and notes that the Supreme Court has interpreted the “right to life” as encompassing the right to live in a healthy environment. Simultaneously, India situates these commitments within a broader developmental framework and justifies its inability to comply with international commitments on the basis of its “development” needs. For instance, in paragraph 31, it states: *“India submitted its Nationally Determined Contribution under the Paris Agreement on a ‘best effort basis’, keeping its developmental imperatives in mind.”*¹²

This illustrates how HRJs may be articulated alongside, and at times conditioned by, considerations of economic development, thereby reflecting the balancing of human rights obligations with broader policy priorities.

Finland employs HRJs when addressing the climate crisis, environmental degradation, and biodiversity loss in its national report. It emphasizes that these issues are “linked with many human rights,” including the rights of Indigenous peoples and children, and further frames

¹¹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, p. 14, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/development/desa/secretariat/humanrights/indicators/1621-usa.html) [accessed 18 December 2023].

¹² UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, p. 5-6, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/development/desa/secretariat/humanrights/indicators/41ind1.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

its climate mitigation, adaptation, and biodiversity efforts as necessary to ensure the full realization of fundamental and human rights.¹³ In doing so, Finland extends the scope of HRJs beyond traditional civil and political rights into the domain of environmental governance and sustainable development. This illustrates how HRJs can function as a flexible and expansive justificatory tool, allowing States to connect a wide range of policy areas, such as action and the Sustainable Development Goals, to the broader human rights framework. As such, human rights are invoked not only to justify specific measures, but to provide an overarching normative rationale that links diverse policy objectives to the realization of rights at both national and international levels.

In the reporting of the legislative and institutional guarantees of human rights, Russia uses HRJs in its national report and explains that human rights “determine the purpose, content and application of laws and the activities of the legislature”. Following this, it is expressed that the “President of the Russian Federation is the guarantor” of human rights.¹⁴ In this sense, HRJs are not used to justify specific policies, but to frame the entirety of legislative activity as inherently grounded in human rights principles. Moreover, they extend to legitimizing central political authority, in this case the role of the President. This example illustrates the flexibility of HRJs as a justificatory tool, through which the State can invoke human rights in its own interest, rather than as narrowly applied or issue-specific arguments. Russia’s misuse of the UPR is explored below in more detail.

Not all examples of the arguments that States use to justify their actions fit with the definition of a Human Rights Justification, i.e. not directly couched in language related to human rights. With reference to the recommendations of ratification of Conventions that Sweden has not accepted, Sweden addresses these in its national report and argues in different ways to support its stand. Concerning the Third Optional Protocol to the

¹³ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Finland*, 5 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/FIN/1, p. 16, available at: [G2244387.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

¹⁴ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 3, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

Convention on the Rights of the Child on a communications procedure, Sweden states that “if children are to be able to have their rights upheld, it is important that there are systems in place that enable them to assert them”. Sweden continues to state that “these rights can be asserted in different ways” and that the potential ratification of the Third Optional Protocol must be analyzed further before the Government can take a stance on the issue.¹⁵ Regarding the recommendation to ratify the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, Sweden argues that the provisions of the Convention “are to a wide extent also regulated in legal acts of the EU” and that a discussion to potentially ratify the Convention must therefore be addressed at EU level. The State argues that this means that a unilateral approach “is not possible” and thereafter mentions that no other EU Member State has ratified the Convention.

These are not examples of HRJs in its strictest sense but rather illustrate how States may rely on alternative forms of justification that are not explicitly grounded in human rights norms. Instead, Sweden draws on procedural, institutional, and legal arguments to support its position. In the case of the Third Optional Protocol, the emphasis is placed on the existence of domestic mechanisms and the need for further governmental analysis, reflecting a cautious, process-oriented justification. Similarly, in relation to the Convention on Migrant Workers, Sweden invokes legal competence at the EU level and the constraints of regional governance, alongside a reference to the practice of other EU Member States.

In conclusion, the reporting system of the UPR is, in itself, embedded within a human rights framework, which may have implications for the use of HRJs as well as other forms of argumentation. Given that the national reports serve as self-assessment documents detailing human rights progress, challenges, and the implementation of past recommendations, States are not only expected but institutionally encouraged to frame their actions and decisions in human rights language. Therefore, the prevalence of HRJs in such reports may, at least in part, reflect the normative and procedural constraints of the

¹⁵ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Sweden*, 11 November 2019, A/HRC/WG.6/35/SWE/1, p. 4, available at: [G1932124.pdf \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/sites/unorg/files/2019/11/G1932124.pdf) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

reporting mechanism itself, where States are obliged to demonstrate engagement with human rights norms. Consequently, the arguments presented in this setting are likely to have been shaped by expectations of compliance and legitimacy, which may influence both the selection and formulation of justifications.

It should be noted that, while the study of the UPR provides a useful channel for comparing the diplomatic use of human rights rhetoric among four jurisdictions in this project (Sweden, Finland, India, and Ukraine), as well as in contrast to the United States, China, and Russia, the project's fifth jurisdiction, Taiwan, is excluded from this forum. On the other hand, Taiwan's human rights development has not been shaped by the evolution of the UPR, as its domestication of UN human rights conventions has primarily been carried out by mirroring the treaty bodies' review procedures rather than those of the UPR.¹⁶

Russia's use of HRJ in Defense of its Invasion of Ukraine

A glaring example of how a State uses HRJs on the international horizontal level is Russia when justifying the full-scale invasion of Ukraine.

Note: This section is reproduced from Maria Grahn-Farley¹⁷, How to Counter Attempts by Authoritarian States to Redefine the Concept of Human Rights: Russia's Use of Human Rights Justifications in Defense of its Invasion of Ukraine in Reconstructing Power and Hegemony in Public International Law (eds., Mark Klamberg, Katinka Svanberg & Love Rönnelid, Springer, 2026).

¹⁶ For an overview on Taiwan's domestication of UN human rights convention, see Institutional Human Rights Protection without a UN-membership: Taiwan's Domestication of International Human Rights Law, 2-3.

¹⁷ Maria Grahn-Farley, How to Counter Attempts by Authoritarian States to Redefine the Concept of Human Rights: Russia's Use of Human Rights Justifications in Defense of its Invasion of Ukraine, in Reconstructing Power and Hegemony in Public International Law (eds., Mark Klamberg, Katinka Svanberg & Love Rönnelid, Springer, 2026).

On the international stage, one example where the shift from human rights as understood as a universal normative regime binding all nations equally is how Russia uses HRJs to justify its 2022 invasion of Ukraine. The Council of Europe's expulsion of the Russian Federation meant that Russia was no longer a member of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), a situation that continues at the time of writing. The United Nations chose a different approach: they suspended Russia from the United Nations Human Rights Council but did not expel Russia from the UN Human Rights regimes (such as human rights conventions). These actions mean that whilst Russia is no longer a part to the ECHR, it is still a party to the UN Human Rights treaties into which it had already entered and therefore retains its legal obligations under the UN human rights regimes.

Russia has commonly used two HRJs, which were expressed by their Minister of Foreign Affairs Sergey Lavrov on an almost a weekly basis at the time of the invasion are: one, to protect Russian-speaking minorities in Ukraine, and two, to protect the right to Russian culture.

Russia has also taken advantage of the UN Human Rights regime for both justifying and arguing that its actions were legitimate, seeking to deflect international criticism. The technique was to use a direct reference to the HRJs referenced above, being that the invasion of Ukraine was in fulfilment of the positive obligation to protect Russian speaking people in Ukraine and the positive obligation to protect Russian minority culture in Ukraine. In response to human rights or public international law criticism, Russia argued that the fact it was meeting positive obligations towards protecting the minority rights of Russian speakers in Ukraine (in other words, that its actions were driven by action to protect human rights) meant that this criticism was proof of "Russia Phobia".

Russia then took advantage of the character of the UN Periodic Review procedures. This two-review process (examined in the book chapter) comprises the State Reports submitted to the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, and the State Reports submitted to the UN

Committee against Racial Discrimination. In all of the reporting systems of the Core UN Human Rights treaties, the Concluding Observations follow a specific format: they begin with praise, followed by a critique, and end with final words of praise. Following this format - the Rights of the Child Committee begins by giving Russia praise for its child rights agenda and the national child rights program (the Decade of Childhood and Government Order No. 122-2 of 23 January 2021). This program is headed by the Child Rights Commissioner Maria Alekseyevna Lvova-Belova, for whom the International Criminal Court has issued an arrest warrant for being “allegedly responsible for the war crime of unlawful deportation of population (children) and that of unlawful transfer of population (children) from occupied areas of Ukraine to the Russian Federation (under articles 8(2)(a)(vii) and 8(2)(b)(vii) of the Rome Statute. Although the kidnapping is criticized in the middle of the Concluding Observation, nonetheless the section concludes with praise again and a hope to see further implementation of the national child programme, despite this being headed by the very same person wanted by the International Criminal Court for kidnapping Ukrainian children. Russia’s actions show that the UN periodic report system is unfit to deal with Russia’s human rights violations because its focus is on measuring the compliance of a State, so it is much more difficult for this human rights regime to respond to a State which is using human rights as an instrument of governance.

By using HRJs to defend its invasion in combination with its continued active role within the UN human rights regime, even if not as a participant in the Human Rights Council, Russia has created an argument where every human rights critique against Russia is dismissed as an expression of Russia Phobia (usually the middle part of a Concluding Observation) or indeed validates any praise of Russia (as with the programme of the Decade of Childhood and Government – placed in the beginning of a Concluding Observation). Whilst this may not change the minds of States and individuals who are already critical of Russia’s behavior, it provides a “human rights” gloss to Russia’s international allies and within Russia.

India's use of Human Rights Justification-like arguments (“related notions”) under General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT)

We have found that HRJs are highly contextual and subject specific. For instance, we have found a limited use of HRJs in the strict sense in our research within climate. This can be partly explained by the scope of the studies on climate, as they are mostly limited to the research on climate-related litigation (only EU legislative acts have additionally been considered, and they are, as such, referred to in Deliverable 7.7 authored by Chiara Antoniazzi) and partly because they more commonly use language that is related to human rights but does not exactly cite a specific right. We have identified that there is a fine line between a HRJ and what we are describing as “related notions” i.e. notions related to human rights, and that sometimes States use slightly different language or arguments depending on the forum.

One case submitted to the WTO dispute settlement, which concerns India, one of the five countries subject of this study, stands out. Here the government refers to “sustainable development” rather than specifically to “the Right to Development”.

This summary is based on research by Caterina Milo and concerns the use of the Right to Development in the sense of “sustainable development”.

In re: *India — Certain Measures Relating to Solar Cells and Solar Modules, WT/DS456*, the United States challenged domestic content requirements under India's Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission, arguing that they discriminated against imported solar cells and modules, thereby violating international trade law. India defended the measures as limited in scope, not amounting to a prohibition on imports, and claimed they were justified under Article XX of the GATT as being essential to secure products in short supply or to comply with laws and regulations.

India argued that electricity constitutes a basic human necessity and that the measures were taken to address sustainable development needs. It stressed that the measures were designed to ensure: “ecologically sustainable growth, fundamental to which is the concept of sustainable development, in that India's energy requirements to fuel its economic growth

would need to be achieved in a sustainable manner”. Moreover, India submitted that the contested measures were part of its compliance with its international law obligations relating to climate change.

Dismissing India’s case, the Panel appointed by the World Trade Organization (WTO) to adjudicate on the dispute found that India’s measures violated Article III:4 of the GATT and Article 2.1 of the Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) Agreement, as they treated imported products less favorably than domestic ones. The Panel also rejected India’s justifications under Articles XX(j) and XX(d) of the GATT, finding that there was no proven risk of short supply and that the measures were not necessary to comply with any legal obligations. The Appellate Body of the WTO ultimately upheld the Panel’s findings.¹⁸

Although they were dismissed, these arguments show an interesting use of human rights justifications reasoning (as it is unusual for a WTO case to contain human rights elements) and also includes a nod to international law obligations related to climate change.

EU and the World Health Organization (WHO)

This text is taken from a report by Swarup Sarkar, UGOT^{19 20}

Epidemics, migration, climate, and gender are not independent domains of human rights; rather, they intersect and shape each other’s outcomes. The COVID-19 pandemic clearly demonstrated how these interactions influence both the spread of disease and its social and economic consequences. International travel, largely driven in the early phase by wealthier populations, contributed to the rapid global spread of COVID-19. However, the impact of containment measures—particularly travel restrictions and lockdowns—fell

¹⁸ WTO Panel Report, *India — Certain Measures Relating to Solar Cells and Solar Modules*, WT/DS456/R, adopted 24 July 2017; WTO Appellate Body Report, *India — Certain Measures Relating to Solar Cells and Solar Modules*, WT/DS456/AB/R, adopted 16 September 2016.

¹⁹ MD MS, University of Gothenburg, Sweden; Global Health Security Network, Australia; Ex Director/Adviser World Health Organisation, Global Fund, UNAIDS, Asian Development Bank, UNITAID, CARE International; Ex CG Pandit National Chair, Indian Council of Medical Research.

²⁰ WP 2 Reclaiming Human Rights for Effective Epidemic Control: Lessons from COVID-19 – a suggested policy approach for the EU, Swarup Sarkar, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19865020.

disproportionately on poorer countries and vulnerable population groups within countries. This pattern is not unique to COVID-19. Diseases such as dengue may be introduced through global mobility, yet their impact is most severe in communities with limited access to health services. Even in high-income regions, including parts of Europe, preparedness for emerging or re-emerging diseases such as dengue or other tropical conditions remains inadequate.

Epidemic responses tend to amplify existing inequalities.²¹ Marginalized communities, migrants, and informal workers often experience reduced access to essential services while bearing the greatest economic and social burden of public health measures. These populations, particularly those who are socially disadvantaged and have limited or no alternatives, are most affected by disruptions in livelihoods and healthcare access.

Gender is another critical dimension shaping epidemic outcomes. During COVID-19, women in many settings experienced higher exposure due to caregiving roles and overcrowded living conditions. Although mortality rates were often lower among women, they faced increased vulnerability to infection in confined environments, disruption of essential services such as maternal and reproductive healthcare, and heightened risks of violence and economic loss. These gendered impacts underscore the need to go beyond mortality indicators and adopt a broader understanding of equity in epidemic responses.

At the same time, COVID-19 revealed a significant shift in the role of human rights. Traditionally, human rights have functioned as a mechanism to protect individuals from State overreach. During COVID-19, however, they were increasingly revoked by States to justify restrictive measures in the name of public health. This phenomenon, described as Human Rights Justifications (HRJ), represents a transition from human rights as tools of accountability to instruments of governance, often prioritizing population-level objectives over individual protections.

²¹ Marmot, M., & Allen, J. (2020). COVID-19: exposing and amplifying inequalities. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 74(9), 681–682. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2020-214720>

Vertical Intra-State Use of Human Rights Justifications (HRJs), within Countries and across Topics

We have mapped the use of HRJs within municipal regimes in Sweden, Finland, Taiwan, Ukraine and India, and focused on a range of themes to enable relevant comparisons to be made:

Migration and COVID-19 within Sweden

COVID-19 within Finland

Migration and COVID-19 within Taiwan

Migration and the role of the EU in relation to Ukraine

Right to Development in climate change

A more general approach with regard to India.

We have not sought to follow a strict legal comparative method between countries or topics. Instead, we have focused on the function of HRJs in the above-mentioned contexts, and how the function differs from country to country, and between topics. The typology described below is place-based and only categorizes the various functions of HRJs. As such the typology does not constitute a theoretical analytical claim about what a Human Rights Justification is – as an ontological phenomenon.

By focusing on different places, we have also been able to generate different typologies that reflect how HRJs are used in different places, even for the same theme. Although there is a clear overlap between how States are using HRJs there are also some place-based variations. For instance, the studies on COVID-19 and Migration across countries have identified the following versions of HRJs as forms of State governance, as described by Laura Carlson in: *The Changing Paradigm of Human Rights Justifications: Challenges for Civil*

Society, Zbornik znanstvenih 85 (Ljubljana Law Review) (2025)²² and Maria Grahn-Farley²³ in The Silent Sound of Drowning: Human Rights Justifications and Complex Intersectionality, 51 Brooklyn Journal of International Law (2025):

- 1) By directly appealing to a human right as a justification.
- 2) By misrepresenting the ordinary meaning of the treaty text used as a justification.
- 3) By using the UN human rights doctrine as justification
- 4) By using international public law principles as justifications.

Carlson and Grahn-Farley's typology does not take a stance on whether the HRJ in itself is "good or bad." Instead, it aims at identifying whether the State is using HRJs to expand human rights, or to avoid its human rights obligations.

In a forthcoming article, entitled *The Doctrinal Void, Human Rights Justifications and Positive Obligations under the European Convention of Human Rights*, forthcoming in *Juridisk Tidskrift 2026*²⁴, Maria Nääv analyzes the relationship between HRJs and positive obligations in the system under the European Convention of Human Rights. Nääv observes that the European Court of Human Rights' (ECtHR) jurisprudence regarding positive obligations generally concerns cases where the State has infringed their positive obligations through omissions.

In the case of HRJs, the opposite applies: the State has acted and explained its action through human rights. Due to the open-ended character of the positive obligations, a distinction between the two is only possible in the concrete application of a Human Rights Justification in the ECtHR. As the Court's jurisprudence follows a reversed logic, it offers little guidance in determining the legality of a HRJ invoked by a State as an argument for

²² Laura Carlson, The Changing Paradigm of Human Rights Justifications: Challenges for Civil Society, Zbornik znanstvenih 85 (Ljubljana Law Review) (2025).

²³ Maria Grahn-Farley, The Silent Sound of Drowning: Human Rights Justifications and Complex Intersectionality, 51 Brooklyn Journal of International Law (2025).

²⁴ The Doctrinal Void, Human Rights Justifications and Positive Obligations under the European Convention of Human Rights, forthcoming in *Juridisk Tidskrift 2026*,

legislation, leaving a gap where such arguments are unregulated. Nääv concludes that - at its core - this gap gives rise to a legal grey zone wherein Contracting States may rely on positive obligations to justify their actions and decisions, while simultaneously evading judicial scrutiny under the very same obligations, severely challenging the State's accountability and transparency.

Ukraine

In her study on how HRJs have been used in Ukraine to build a shared identity with Europe, based on the shared values of human rights and democracy, Olena Chernenko sees HRJs as part of articulating and expanding human rights in Ukraine, an expansion that was crucial for the activation of the EU Mass Directive making it possible for Ukrainians to flee to and resettle in EU Member States through an abbreviated process.

The material below is taken from Chernenko's text in the report: *Olena, Chernenko, HRJust WP5 – Migration, Production of theme-specific reports including recommendations on how policy, regulations and law can be adapted to better protect fundamental rights of migrants, Paul Lappalainen (Lead author)*²⁵.

Issues. Ukraine is a sender state in the migration/refugee context. With regard to Ukrainian refugees, the EU has used HRJs in a positive light, extending the Temporary Protection Directive's protection to Ukrainians in EU Member States. Before Russia's military aggression against Ukraine in 2014, Ukrainian migration to the EU was mainly labor based. Since the aggression was "limited", Ukrainians could move to safer areas within the country. However, the Russian invasion in February 2022 led to a substantial forced migration out of Ukraine, resulting in an unprecedented migration challenge for EU countries, even greater than the challenge in 2015-2017. The influx from Ukraine due to the war led the EU to activate

²⁵ Olena, Chernenko, HRJust WP5 – Migration, Production of theme-specific reports including recommendations on how policy, regulations and law can be adapted to better protect fundamental rights of migrants, Paul Lappalainen (Lead author).

the European Union's Temporary Protection Directive (TPD) ²⁶ on 4 March 2022 to ensure displaced persons have immediate, harmonized rights across EU Member States, allowing them to bypass lengthy, individual asylum procedures.

Though originally anticipated to be in effect for a maximum of 3 years as an emergency mechanism, it is now being continued until at least 4 March 2027²⁷ and has already reached the 5-year threshold. First applied for an initial period of one year, until 4 March 2023, the Directive was then automatically extended for one additional year until 4 March 2024, then by Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2023/2409²⁸ – until 4 March 2025, by Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2024/1836²⁹ – until 4 March 2026, and by Member States' support on Proposal for a Council implementing Decision extending temporary protection 2022/382³⁰– until 4 March 2027, as mentioned above.

Several HRJs were given as grounds for the unprecedented implementation of the TPD and the granting of all the rights it provides for Ukrainian forced migrants after the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022:

- *the need for human rights protection and solidarity (in the context of the EU as a whole and Member States)* – the EU condemned Russia's aggression and granted temporary protection to Ukrainians under the TPD. This response aligns with EU values, particularly

²⁶ Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382 of 4 March 2022 establishing the existence of a mass influx of displaced persons from Ukraine within the meaning of Article 5 of Directive 2001/55/EC and having the effect of introducing temporary protection. Available here: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32022D0382>

²⁷ EU Member States Agree to Extend Temporary Protection for Refugees from Ukraine. *Council of the EU Press release 13 June 2025*. Available here: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2025/06/13/eu-member-states-agree-to-extend-temporary-protection-for-refugees-from-ukraine>

²⁸ Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2023/2409 of 19 October 2023 extending temporary protection as introduced by Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382. Available here: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_impl/2023/2409/oj/eng

²⁹ Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2024/1836 of 25 June 2024 extending temporary protection as introduced by Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382. Available here: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_impl/2024/1836/oj

³⁰ Proposal for a COUNCIL IMPLEMENTING DECISION extending temporary protection, as introduced by Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382, until 4 March 2027. Available here: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2025%3A650%3AFIN>

human rights and solidarity (Articles 2, 6, and 21 TEU) and treats the violation of Ukraine's sovereignty as a threat to the wider European community

- *geographical proximity of Ukraine and a security factor for Europe* - Ukraine's proximity and visa-free access facilitated the rapid arrival of war-displaced persons to the EU. The invasion was seen as a broader European security issue, leading to the activation of the TPD in line with the EU's CFSP and Article 21 TEU. The war also reshaped EU security priorities and increased migration pressure on its eastern borders

- *the temporality of protection* - the EU activated temporary protection for Ukrainians in March 2022 and repeatedly extended it until 2027 due to ongoing Russian aggression. Initially seen as short-term, the situation has become prolonged, showing that "temporary" protection may last longer due to continued risks, while still requiring periodic review

- *solidarity of EU Civil Society towards Ukrainians, cultural and historical proximity* - strong public support, shared European identity, and cultural proximity played a key role in activating and extending the TPD. Civil Society initially provided rapid assistance and influenced EU decisions based on human rights, while later the EU ensured continued support through legal mechanisms despite growing "compassion fatigue".

Ukrainians have thereby been granted various rights that are similar to those of residents. Meanwhile, these provisions are **temporary**, as the very name of this Directive indicates. As the war has dragged on for years, the unconditional positivity of these unprecedented prolongations has become a significant discussion in its own right within the international law agenda on war-affected individuals. As Ukrainian adults have become increasingly established throughout the Member States under the umbrella of the TPD and national legislation of each of Member State since 2022, what kinds of choices should be made concerning their future, and in particular, concerning their children is still an open question

(the gender breakdown of Ukrainian refugees, following the initial influx in the first months, still consists predominantly of younger and middle-aged women with dependent children³¹).

Taiwan

This section is drawn from text authored by Ya-Wen Yang in *HRJust WP 5 – Migration, Production of theme-specific reports including recommendations on how policy, regulations and law can be adapted to better protect fundamental rights of migrants*, Paul Lapalinen (lead author)³².

In her work on HRJs in Taiwan, Ya-Wen Yang has - in addition to the above categories - added one which she calls “paternalistic” which means that the HRJ is said to be for the protection of one human right by limiting another right or the same right.³³ An example of this is to frame migrant workers’ rights as being in conflict with nationals’ rights, HRJs in Taiwan’s migration context also tend to be paternalistic. Restrictions on, or insufficient protections of, migrants’ rights are often articulated through the rhetoric of protecting migrant workers. This is also a notably gendered phenomenon, as it is more frequently observed where those affected are predominantly female, such as foreign caregivers and family immigrants. For example, the exclusion of foreign caregivers from the Labour Standards Act has been justified on the grounds that workers’ freedom of contract is sufficient, while visa interviews that may be intrusive as to family privacy are said to facilitate immigrants’ right to family reunification.

Shun-Ling Chen observes that HRJs were not invoked to any high degree in the Taiwan context during the actual COVID-19 crisis³⁴. However, she notes a shift in the use of the right to health from being an individual right to becoming a matter of public health. This shift,

³¹ Three Years of War in Ukraine: We Must Support Women-Centered Refugee Solutions. *February 24, 2025*. Available here: <https://refugees.org/three-years-of-war-in-ukraine-we-must-support-women-centered-refugee-solutions/>

³² Ya-Wen Yang in *HRJust WP 5 – Migration, Production of theme-specific reports including recommendations on how policy, regulations and law can be adapted to better protect fundamental rights of migrants*, Paul Lapalinen (lead author)

³³ Ya-Wen Yang, see Deliverable 3.2 outlining the theory of human rights justifications.

³⁴ WP 4 Taiwan - final report 4, page 2

without measures to protect minorities, risks becoming a majoritarian instrument justifying the rights of the many over the one.³⁵ A human right is individual and concrete in its nature for the very purpose as being a protection of the individual against the collective. In addition, Chen observes the transformation of this right from an individual and concrete right to an abstract and communal generates a risk of function creep (addressed below).³⁶

Finland

The following text is drawn from the report: How States Invoke Human Rights to Justify Their (In)Actions by Milka Sormunen and Tuomas Ojanen, University of Helsinki. Whilst in practice this approach largely overlaps with the previously described categories of HRJs, it takes a different perspective, one of compliance, examining the legitimacy and the illegitimacy of the use of HRJs.

Milka Sormunen and Tuomas Ojanen have reviewed HRJs connected to the legislative process in Finland and considered the use of HRJs from a critical perspective. They propose a new legal framework for critically analyzing strategies of illegitimate HRJs, and in so doing they demonstrate how strategic use of human rights language can serve to shield State behavior from scrutiny and reduce accountability. Their analysis explores strategies or techniques of misappropriation and examines the types of arguments used when misappropriating human rights. Their review of case studies from the Finnish legislative process includes the legislative proposal concerning a temporary lockdown act³⁷. The Finnish constitutional *ex ante* review offers a good environment to analyze HRJs because of the nature of the procedure in which the government explains the motivations for proposing a law, after which the Constitutional Law Committee of the Parliament assesses the compatibility of the proposal with human rights. In identifying an illegitimate HRJ, they propose the criterion of not being in accordance with the criteria for limiting human rights.

³⁵ Deliverable 4.1, p. 53; for specific cases see final report 2, p. 3-4; see also WP 4 and 5 Project Highlight and Roundtable, p. 2

³⁶ See WP4 final report 4

³⁷ Government Bill (HE) 39/2021 Hallituksen esitys eduskunnalle laiksi liikkumisvapauden ja lähikontaktien väliaikaisesta rajoittamisesta.

These criteria are grounded both in Finnish constitutional law and human rights law and therefore form a suitable yardstick to assess Finnish constitutional review.

They have identified these five categories of HRJs:

- 1) Mis-definition of the extent of obligations: this occurs when States exaggerate or downplay their duties, in order to justify action or inaction. For example, the legislative proposal concerning a temporary lockdown act relied too extensively on positive obligations to justify limitations of other rights.
- 2) Mis-definition of the scope of a right: this involves inaccurately narrowing or expanding the legal boundaries of a right.
- 3) Misclassification of absolute rights: refers to treating non-derogable rights as if they can be limited or balanced against other interests.
- 4) Misclassification of interests as rights entails presenting political or security concerns as human rights in order to legitimize restrictive measures.
- 5) Vulnerabilization - a category identified by Sormunen and Ojanen, meaning the practice of granting rights selectively based on perceived vulnerability, creating hierarchies that exclude others from protection.

A key analytical distinction in the report is between legitimate and illegitimate human rights justifications. Legitimate justifications are grounded in the accepted legal framework governing human rights obligations, including the distinction between negative and positive obligations and the cumulative criteria for permissible limitations, such as legality, legitimate aim, necessity, proportionality, and respect for the essence of the right. Illegitimate justifications, by contrast, fail to comply with these criteria. Importantly, Sormunen and Ojanen do not treat every controversial or contested interpretation as illegitimate but acknowledge reasonable disagreement. Instead, they focus on patterns of argumentation that systematically distort rights in ways detrimental to their protective function.

The fifth is vulnerabilization, whereby access to rights is conditioned on proving vulnerability, creating hierarchies of deservingness and excluding those who do not meet narrow criteria. Under the instrumentalization law, for example, asylum seekers at the border would only gain access to normal procedures if border guards deemed them vulnerable or at risk of inhuman treatment. Rights protection thus became dependent on an informal assessment of vulnerability, transforming vulnerability from a basis for enhanced protection into a gatekeeping tool for denying rights to others.

The report situates these Finnish examples within broader global trends of human rights misappropriation, drawing parallels with illiberal regimes that use human rights rhetoric to entrench power and undermine democratic norms. By offering a structured framework for analyzing human rights justifications, the report contributes to the theoretical understanding of how legal language can be strategically deployed to shield state behavior from scrutiny. The typology presented serves as a diagnostic tool for identifying argumentative distortions and enhancing accountability in rights-based governance.

Human Rights Justifications as a way to build interdependency and a foundation based on shared values: the Ukraine example

Although many examples, for instance in the treatment of the rights of migrants in both Sweden and Taiwan, the term “Human Rights Justification” does not necessarily mean a limitation of an existing human right. In Ukraine for example HRJs have been important for the advancement of Ukraine as a liberal democracy ever since its independence and with a heightened focus in recent years. Olena Chernenko describes Ukraine’s use of human rights as part of creating the foundations for a liberal democratic identity shared with the EU and its Member States. These shared values and identities facilitated and motivated the activation of the Temporary Protection Directive (TPD) and also helped facilitate its extension.

Authored by Olena Chernenko, the text draws on: Olena Chernenko & Martin Westlund, Why the Temporary Protection Directive was Activated: Solidarity, Geopolitics, and Humanitarian Considerations, 2 Europa Rättsligtidskrift, ERT (2026).³⁸

Chernenko's analysis shows how Ukraine made clear its intention to develop relations with the EU on the principle of integration early in its inception. As early as the Declaration of State Sovereignty of Ukraine in 1990, it was stated that Ukraine "participates directly in the pan-European process and European structures". The 1993 decision of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (the Parliament of Ukraine) declared its aspirations for European integration, stating that the long-term goal and priority of Ukrainian foreign policy was Ukrainian membership of the European communities, as well as other Western European or pan-European structures, as long as those cooperations did not harm its national interests. This landmark document affirmed Ukraine's commitment to integration into European structures and cooperation with Europe. It outlined the aim of concluding a Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with the European Community, which was presented as the first step towards its association and, subsequently, full membership.

This direction was codified in Ukrainian legislation. The Ukrainian Constitution confirms Ukraine's European identity and affirms the irreversibility of Ukraine's European and Euro-Atlantic course. European integration in this context means gradually aligning Ukrainian legislation with EU law. The Law of Ukraine 'On the Principles of Domestic and Foreign Policy' demonstrates the evolution of Ukraine's geopolitical positioning, from defining itself as a 'European non-aligned state' seeking broad cooperation, to emphasizing its European identity and the need to ensure sovereignty, security, and territorial integrity. The Law of Ukraine 'On National Security of Ukraine' made this trajectory explicit, stating that a fundamental principle of national security policy is Ukraine's integration into the European

³⁸ Martin Westlund & Olena Chernenko, Why the Temporary Protection Directive Was Activated: Solidarity, Geopolitics, and Humanitarian Considerations, *Europarättslig Tidskrift*, no. 2, May 2026 (forthcoming).

political, economic, security, and legal space, including accession to the EU and NATO, alongside the development of mutually beneficial relations with other States. Together, these constitutional provisions and legislative acts anchor Ukrainian aspirations to become part of the European political and legal space and demonstrate Ukraine's constitutional self-identification with Europe.

These actions mean that Ukraine is more than a Third Country to the EU. As a result, key steps have been taken by the EU confirming Ukraine's belonging within the EU's sphere. A crucial step was taken in 2014 when the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement was adopted.⁴⁴ It aimed to promote gradual rapprochement of Ukraine and the EU based on shared values, the establishment of enhanced political dialogue, the promotion of regional and international peace and stability, and the progressive integration of Ukraine into the EU's internal market. The Agreement also stressed that respect for democratic principles, human rights, the rule of law, sovereignty, and territorial integrity constitute 'essential elements' of the EU-Ukraine relationship. Another milestone came in 2017, when Ukrainian citizens were granted the right to travel visa-free to the EU for short stays. This was widely presented as a symbol of trust and of Ukraine's anchoring within the European community.

As observed above, when the EU activated the TPD in 2022, it explicitly highlighted this existing visa-free travel regime as part of the justification. Ukrainian nationals already had a legal pathway to enter and move freely within the EU, which made temporary protection a logical continuation of Ukraine's gradual integration³⁹. Humanitarian considerations were central, as EU institutions framed the situation as an exceptional humanitarian emergency requiring swift and collective protection. The decision was also framed in geopolitical terms. EU institutions emphasized Ukraine's visa-free status and deepened ties under the Association Agreement as evidence of a privileged partnership and presented the TPD as an act of solidarity with Ukraine as a European partner. At the same time, Russia's aggression

³⁹ Martin Westlund & Olena Chernenko, *Why the Temporary Protection Directive Was Activated: Solidarity, Geopolitics, and Humanitarian Considerations*, *Europarättslig Tidskrift*, no. 2, May 2026 (forthcoming)

was not only described as a direct threat to Ukraine's sovereignty, but also as a challenge to EU values, stability and security.

The following text by Shun-Ling Chen and her Taiwan team is taken from their report: Institutional Human Rights Protection without a UN-membership: Taiwan's Domestication of International Human Rights Law.

The report demonstrates one way in which a multilateral interdependency can be created within the municipal order. It is through the active engagement of Civil Society and the mirroring of the processes and structures established in the UN Periodic Review, that has enabled Taiwan to develop a similar process at a municipal rather than the international level, one that helps hold the State accountable. In addition, it is through this that Taiwan has been able to create a parallel approach to the horizontal inter-State human rights regimes they are prevented from joining, (to be addressed at length in WP4 Taiwan's final report 1, p. 2-5) maintaining its connection and interdependency with the international treaty regime and its multilateral interdependency.

Voluntary incorporation of International Human Rights Treaties into Domestic Law

Following the democratization transition in the 1990s, the Legislative Yuan (the Congress), pressured by both Civil Society and its own concerns of Taiwan's international standing, ratified the two Covenants. However, Taiwan's attempt to deposit them in the UN Secretariat in 2009 was without success. Subsequently, the Legislative Yuan continued ratifying the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) in 2011, the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) in 2016. However, none of the above-mentioned ratifications could be deposited with and accepted by the UN.

Due to Taiwan's unique status, the Taiwanese government could only be held accountable for international human rights by "domesticating" international human rights standards on the legislative level. To show Taiwan's commitment to follow the international human rights treaties and to ensure their domestic legal effect, Taiwan promulgated several Implementation Acts, which obliged the government to issue State reports and to create an independent international review system. Notably, not all conventions were subject to this procedure, with some remaining unratified by the Legislative Yuan so far (with further details in Appendix A of that report).

"Taiwan Approach"—Unique International Review System in Taiwan

Since 2013, Taiwan has established an alternative international review mechanism, which invited international scholars and experts with prior experience in UN treaty review to participate in the process. This unique review system outperforms the UN system in two ways: 1. it gives NGOs the same amount of time to present parallel/shadow reports to balance out the views prepared by the government; 2. In addition to sessions with government participation, it allows NGOs to have a direct dialogue with international experts on various issues in specially designated sessions. To date, Taiwan has already gone through four rounds of national reports submission and review on the implementation of the two covenants (ICCPR, ICESCR) in accordance with United Nations guidelines in 2012, 2016, 2020, and 2025.

Yet, since Taiwan's voluntary incorporation of the human rights mechanism into its legal order, there is no mechanism to guarantee its compliance. When the government fails to implement its obligations, it faces no corresponding consequences. As the international experts consistently reported since the very first human rights review process, there does not seem to have been much progress on critical issues such as indigenous land dispossession, the enhancement of migrant workers' labor rights, and the enactment of a comprehensive anti-discrimination law. Such observations highlight a consistent structural vulnerability in Taiwan's human rights regime: without accountability, the unilateral

commitment fails to function as a binding obligation but rather as a discretionary exercise of governmental bona fides.

India

Authored by Namita Wahi, text from her report, Human Rights Justifications in India.

Namita Wahi's analysis has focused on the Right to Development which was, for instance, used as a HRJ in the Re: *India — Certain Measures Relating to Solar Cells and Solar Modules*, WT/DS456. She has found that the use of Right to Development as the foundation of a HRJ is part of India's political discourse on the international stage and also domestically by the legislature and the executive - but has not been used to defend State actions against individuals before the judiciary. Analysis suggests that HRJs are seldom used within India: this appears to be because of the strong domestic constitutional framework and historically progressive and activist judiciary. However, this does not preclude the possibility of such uses in the future as the independence of the judiciary from the executive is under increasing threat.⁴⁰

Domestically, all political parties use the development discourse in their election manifestos and political speeches.⁴¹ But India's unified judiciary consisting of the Supreme Court and High Courts has almost never used the RtD to negate human rights to the environment or rights of communities against displacement. To the contrary, in almost all of the cases, both the Supreme Court and the High Courts have interpreted the RtD to uphold compliance with human rights grounded in the "right to life", including the rights to

⁴⁰ V-Dem Institute, *Democracy Report 2024* (University of Gothenburg, 2024); Freedom House, *Freedom in the World 2024: India* (2024); Fali S. Nariman, *Before Memory Fades: An Autobiography* (Hay House India, 2010), on structural pressures on judicial independence in India. See also the Supreme Court Collegium controversy regarding executive non-compliance with judicial appointments. <https://theleaflet.in/judicial-accountability/as-the-supreme-court-collegium-resolutions-on-judge-appointments-open-a-window-a-flurry-of-reactions> (2023).

⁴¹ See, e.g. Indian National Congress, *Congress Manifesto 2024*; Bharatiya Janata Party, *BJP Election Manifesto 2024*; Aam Aadmi Party, *AAP Election Manifesto 2022*. All manifestoes are available at respective party websites. The discourse of "vikas" (development) has been identified as central to Indian electoral politics across party lines; see Pradeep Chhibber and Rahul Verma, *Ideology and Identity: The Changing Party Systems of India* (Oxford University Press, 2018).

education, shelter/housing, education, rights of the child, gender equality and environment. Similar patterns can also be observed before the National Green Tribunal (NGT) where the Tribunal has used the principles of sustainable development to allow development projects with environmental safeguards, although there remain significant gaps in enforcement of the NGT orders.⁴²

This sharp divergence between the approaches of the executive and the judicial branches of the Indian government show that while the fusion of the fields of human rights and economic development have resulted in richer notions of individual freedoms, and textured ideas of distributive justice in political and economic theory and international human rights, in terms of their practical application, the Indian executive continues to ground its “Right to Development” justification for extractive development projects in somewhat utilitarian notions of the “greatest good of the greatest number”, while the courts use existing binding domestic constitutional law and persuasive international law precedents to support and enhance individual human rights using, often citing Sen’s capabilities approach⁴³ to Right to Development. Thus, differing notions of distributive justice underlying approaches of the executive and judicial branches of the Indian state result in their differential treatment of the human rights of individual Indians. This creates a constant tension which is mediated across time depending on the power and legitimacy of different institutions of government.

Summary

The section above gives three different examples, and authored by three different researchers or teams, exploring a place-based understanding of multilateralism in three States which are not EU Members. For instance, the Ukraine example shows how human rights and the use of human rights justification has been an integral part of an holistic approach to create systemic interdependency between EU and Ukraine. For Ukraine, a European country and potentially future EU Member, their approach and the role of human rights is both more systemic but also not as central in an overall strategy towards

⁴² See Namita Wahi, Human Rights Justifications in India.

⁴³ Amartya Sen, Development as Freedom, Oxford University Press (1999, 2001).

interdependency. Although Taiwan's complex international status has meant it is not able to fully participate it has found a way to bind itself to the international horizontal level and has therefore created a multilateral interdependency through human rights, by incorporating a specific instrument which significantly mirrors human rights and the UN human rights regime into its domestic law. India with her own historical context and also in line with dualist international law principles maintains a division between positivist horizontal human rights and an independency when it comes to the legal sphere on the vertical level within the State itself.

It is important to note, that it is not only the place- and the specific context of each country's political and historical realities that make them choose three different ways to relate to multilateralism and its human rights regimes, but that human rights as incorporated into domestic law in ways that allows for law and politics to cross without safeguards will not necessarily mean an expansion of the individual person's human rights, but can also risk creating an environment which can generate human rights justifications that can severely limit people's individual human rights.

Human Rights Justifications by Topic

COVID-19: three countries and three strategies

We compared three countries' strategies to tackle COVID-19: Taiwan using Zero-COVID, the Finnish approach focusing on a hybrid approach - relying on locking down and containing local areas when the spread of COVID19 threatened the limits of hospital capacity, and the Swedish approach with a less explicit strategy, taking a more lenient approach to limiting movement and association. As a result, the use of HRJs varies significantly between the countries.

Taiwan: Zero-COVID

The following text is taken from D4.1, last updated January 2025 authored by Shun-Ling Chen and the Taiwan team

As context, it is useful to note that Taiwan is not a member of the UN and has not been able to deposit the international human rights conventions ratified by the Taiwan Congress. Nevertheless, Taiwan developed a mechanism to implement these conventions, including a periodic review process mirroring that of the UN human rights system.

Taiwan is an island country that is geographically close to China. Despite the unsettled tension between Taiwan and China, there are extended economic ties between the two. Due to the unique geopolitical relationship between Taiwan and China, Taiwan's isolated status as a non-member state in the WHO, and its experience with the 2003 SARS outbreak, the Taiwanese government responded to the COVID-19 pandemic by implementing strict border controls and extensive contact tracing measures.⁴⁴

For more than two years, Taiwan insisted on a Zero-COVID approach, with measures disproportionately affecting specific groups considered to be of higher risk. Although both international and national oversight mechanisms are in place to ensure that the government's action and inaction comply with the standard of human rights protection, the supervisory mechanism's power weakened during the COVID-19 pandemic. During the whole span of the pandemic, the ruling political party also had a congressional majority. The Special Act on COVID-19 had been criticized for granting the administration broad authorization but was never modified until it was sunsetted in 2023. The Control Yuan did not exercise its power of corrective measures even when it expressed concerns that the government's COVID-19 measure violated human rights and went against the rule of law.

⁴⁴ Po-Han Lee & Ying-Chao Kao, Health Apartheid during covid-19: A Decolonial Critique of Racial Politics between Taiwan and the WHO, 5 INT. J. TAIWAN STUD. 375 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1163/24688800-05020006>. Alzbeta Loduhoova & Kristina Kironka: How Did Taiwan Go from 'Most Affected' during sars to 'Least Affected' during covid-19?: A Comparative Study of Taiwan's Emergency Responses, 6 INT. J. TAIWAN STUD. 291 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1163/24688800-20221249>

Taiwan's Constitutional Court also utilized procedural reasoning to dismiss the request to review the constitutionality of the Special Act.

Bearing this context in mind, we further reviewed the extended zero-COVID approach in Taiwan. We found that in implementing quarantine measures - such as mandatory quarantine, digital surveillance, and in one case in October 2022, the de-facto deprivation of quarantined individuals' voting rights - the Taiwanese government seldom found the need to use HRJs other than very broad brush claims to protect the right to life and health – if not promoting public health alone – to legitimize its pandemic measures. This may also have something to do with the fact that Taiwan is not fully integrated into the international human rights system and relies on domestication of international human rights covenants.

Finland: hybrid strategy

The section on Finland and Sweden reflects key points in the more detailed analysis in Deliverable D4.1 authored by Milka Sormunen

Finland's 'hybrid strategy' included a combination of both soft law and hard law measures, including the use of emergency powers during the state of emergency declared by Finland both in Spring 2020 and Spring 2021. The Constitutional Law Committee of Parliament played a major role in the ex-ante review of various COVID-19-related legislative measures and governmental decrees adopted under the Emergency Powers Act for their compatibility with the Constitution and international human rights treaties. This ex-ante constitutional review of legislation by the Committee allowed Finland to refrain from adopting a number of unconstitutional measures. The main HRJ in Finland was the positive obligation to protect the rights to life and health. Regarding several measures, this positive obligation was understood too broadly, which resulted in overly limiting other rights.

Sweden: lenient measures

In contrast, Sweden introduced only minimal measures to limit public gatherings and mostly relied on recommendations on social distancing to curb the pandemic. Coercive regulatory instruments, such as visit bans to care homes, were used only when absolutely necessary and at the later stages of the pandemic. Sweden was among the few countries that refrained from introducing strict lockdown measures or hard law measures entailing significant interferences with human rights.

Especially in the early stages of the pandemic, Sweden relied on voluntary behavioral changes, considering them to be not only sufficient and sustainable but also lawful and compatible with fundamental and human rights. The Swedish approach was characterized by a prominent role of experts in public discussion, which reflects has the focus of the Swedish policy-making process on gathering knowledge ahead of policy formulation, and the health-related character of the crisis. The role of expert evidence was substantial in defining Sweden's COVID-19 strategy.

Sweden relied on a strict understanding of the proportionality principle but failed to express clearly which factors were considered most significant in the proportionality analysis. Consequently, HRJs were not prominent in Sweden's approach except concerning keeping schools open, which was regarded as a way to protect the health of children and young people and their rights.

The Swedish government appointed a Commission of Inquiry (Coronakommissionen, directive 2020:74) charged with investigating Sweden's COVID measures. In 2022, the Commission issued two reports, the first focusing on the economic effects of the pandemic and the second on its effects on people, including fundamental rights. According to the reports, the pandemic has impacted people both directly, through COVID rates and mortality, and indirectly, through factors such as delayed care, limited opportunities to earn one's living and increased risk of unemployment. The Commission concluded that the

pandemic has negatively impacted on people, especially those already in a vulnerable position, both in terms of health and economy.

India and the use of Human Rights Justification and the Right to Development, a Segway to Climate

Authored by Namita Wahi, text from her report “Human Rights Justifications in India”.

The articulation of the “Right to Development (RtD)” in international law as both an individual and collective right has been grounded in both the “right to life” and the “right to self-determination”. Within the Indian constitutional context, the RtD has been articulated mostly in environmental cases derived from international law principles pertaining to “sustainable development” and the human “Right to Life”. Other cases have occasionally referenced the RtD as part of the “Right to Life” as well as principles of relevant international conventions like the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW).

The executive branch of the Indian Government has used the “Right to Development” as a justification for both its compliance and non-compliance with its international obligations as part of the Universal Periodic Review.⁴⁵ Domestically, however, the government has weaponized laws to financially choke non-governmental organisations and Civil Society actors and thereby prevent the use of speech and advocacy, and the organisation of protests against development projects by individuals and communities whose human rights to land, water, forests, environment, housing, shelter are negatively impacted by these projects.⁴⁶

⁴⁵ India, National Report submitted to the UN Human Rights Council for the Universal Periodic Review, *4th UPR Cycle*, UN Doc A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1 (17 August 2022), paras. 5–6 (invoking the right to sustainable development and the right to development in the context of India’s development policies); see also India’s submissions in prior UPR cycles (2008, 2012, 2017).

⁴⁶ See, e.g., the Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Amendment Act, 2020 (India), which imposed significant restrictions on foreign funding to civil society organisations and non-governmental organisations, widely reported to have curtailed the operational capacity of organisations engaged in advocacy, research, and community mobilisation

The Indian executive has also occasionally used “development” as a justification for projects that have displaced communities or caused environmental harm, although it has never used this as the sole justification in any case. In all cases, “development” is used as a supporting justification for the Government’s action grounded otherwise in domestic law. In none of the decided cases by both the Supreme Court and the High Courts, has the Court’s decision turned solely on the “right to development”, although it has been used along with principles like the “precautionary principle” and the “public trust doctrine” to justify the Court’s decision in a few cases. The Court has never used the RtD to negate human rights to the environment or rights of communities against displacement.

We can therefore conclude that the executive branch of the Indian State has often used the “Right to Development” as a HRJ on the international plane, and also in the past decade has weaponized domestic laws against organisations that seek to inform, educate, research and to organise communities against harmful effects of development projects. However, the Indian judiciary has never upheld the use of the “right to development” as the sole justification for grounding relief in any of the 148 Supreme Court and High Court cases that have been decided by courts so far. In almost all of the cases, both the Supreme Court and the High Courts have interpreted the RtD to uphold compliance with human rights grounded in the right to life, including the rights to education, shelter/housing, education, rights of the child, gender equality and environment.

Climate litigation and the use of “related notions”

Researched by Chiara Tea Antoniazzi and Caterina Milo (drawn from Chiara Tea Antoniazzi and Caterina Milo’s report: “Related Notions”, last updated December 2025)

In the area of climate change, a noteworthy trend was found of States having recourse to arguments that are not strictly human rights-based but rely on notions that are connected

against government development projects. See also Amnesty International India, *India: Weaponizing Laws Against Civil Society* (2021).

to human rights. Examples of such notions in connection with climate change include sustainable development, the protection of health, the welfare state, intergenerational equity, and consumers' interests.

With regard to dispute settlement before the World Trade Organization (WTO), express references to human rights in general by State parties to a dispute are almost non-existent. Nonetheless, international trade law includes a specific system of exceptions (e.g., the general exceptions outlined in Article XX of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT)), which offer leeway for States to justify their measures using related notions. These are mainly the exceptions outlined in letters (a), "public morals", (b), measures "necessary to protect human, animal or plant life or health", and (g), measures "relating to the conservation of exhaustible natural resources". For this reason, States and the EU have often referred, for example, to the need to protect human health (Canada – Certain Measures Affecting the Renewable Energy Generation Sector, WT/DS412 / Canada – Measures Relating to the Feed-In Tariff Program, WT/DS426; European Union – Certain Measures Concerning Palm Oil and Oil Palm Crop-Based Biofuels, WT/DS593; European Union and Certain Member States – Certain Measures Concerning Palm Oil and Oil Palm Crop-Based Biofuels, WT/DS600). References can also be found to notions like sustainable development. This happened, for example, in India – Certain Measures Relating to Solar Cells and Solar Modules, WT/DS456 (see above).

Within investor-State dispute settlement⁴⁷, States also rarely use direct references to their human rights obligations to justify their conduct before arbitral tribunals. More frequent is the use of arguments based on related notions, by incorporating human rights-related considerations into the arguments employed to legitimize their conduct under their right to regulate, i.e., the right that permits host States to regulate in derogation of the commitments they undertook towards investors.

⁴⁷ This paragraph on investment arbitration is based on Caterina Milo, "Environmental and Human Rights Justifications in Investment Arbitration: Probing the Limits of ISDS for the Adjudication of Climate-Related Disputes", *Journal of World Investment & Trade* 26 (2025) 1–45.

States have first of all resorted to related notions – in particular, the protection of human health and of local ecosystems – to justify their climate action. Examples are *Rockhopper Exploration Plc, Rockhopper Italia S.p.A. and Rockhopper Mediterranean Ltd v. Italian Republic*, where Italy justified its ban on offshore oil drilling near its coastline, citing environmental and social considerations; and *Eco Oro v. Colombia*, where Colombia justified its choice to implement measures prohibiting mining activities in certain areas on the grounds that these measures were aimed at protecting the local ecosystems.

Secondly and more frequently, States have justified their actions with negative impacts on investments in more sustainable energy sources by invoking the need to protect consumers and the welfare of their citizens as the public interest justifying their conduct. Examples are *SolEs Badajoz GmbH v. Kingdom of Spain*, *ESPF Beteiligungs GmbH, ESPF Nr. 2 Austria Beteiligungs GmbH*, and *InfraClass Energie 5 GmbH & Co. KG v. Italian Republic and Encavis and others v. Italian Republic*.

Apart from these sectoral contexts, related notions have also been used by States, for instance, before the European Court of Human Rights with a view to claiming a wide margin of appreciation in the adoption of climate measures (or lack thereof): e.g., in its reply to the application in *Greenpeace Nordic and Others v. Norway*, the Norwegian Government referred to the national budget and welfare state as relevant considerations and argued that the choice of measures should be left to the State when considering the consequences of climate measures “including consequences for interests protected under the Convention” and the importance of “participation in democratic processes”.

While the context of litigation and of specific sectors (such as trade and investment) might explain the use of related notions, recourse to related notions also in the context of EU climate legislation (as is shown in Deliverable 7.7) as well as outside the climate area points to possible further reasons, including avoiding the language of rights and obligations while lending legitimacy to the State’s arguments.

The Migrant – the new Colorline

This section draws on work by Ya-Wen Yang and Paul Lappalainen in HRJust WP 5 – Migration, Production of theme-specific reports including recommendations on how policy, regulations and law can be adapted to better protect fundamental rights of migrants, Paul Lappalainen (lead author).

This limited use of HRJs to address the major global challenge of climate change is in stark contrast to the use of HRJs in the treatment of migrants (as distinct from migration). Both Sweden and Taiwan are destination countries for inbound migration, although the categories of migrants differ. Here our research has found similarities between Sweden and Taiwan and the way that HRJs are deployed even though the legal landscape as well as the social, political and historical context is so different between the two countries. Whilst the motivations differ between the two, the structure of the reasoning is similar, following a “paternalistic” approach. Migrants are often regulated through a paternalistic use of HRJs - i.e. limiting certain rights ostensibly for their own benefit, such as to protect other rights. In this way, HRJs imposed on migrants, while appearing to restrict their liberty, may in fact serve as pretexts that obscure underlying sex or racial discrimination.

In Sweden, one example is the government’s argument that the Child Rights Convention (CRC) recognizes collective rights to justify lowering the minimum age of criminal responsibility from fifteen to thirteen. In defending this policy, the government invoked the CRC’s “best interests of the child” principle to prioritize the collective interests of children over the rights of the individual child, leaving the argument open to populist anti-migrant rhetoric and actions.⁴⁸ In Taiwan, the restriction on job mobility for temporary migrant workers means e.g. that low-skilled migrant workers cannot unilaterally terminate their contracts within the three-year term unless their employer is at fault, which in turn severely limits migrant workers’ right to work. The Taiwanese government justifies this policy as

⁴⁸ Maria Grahn-Farley (2025) ‘THE SILENT SOUND OF DROWNING: Human Rights Justifications and Complex Intersectionality’, 51 *Brook. J. Int’l L.* 1, 12.

necessary to protect the right to work of Taiwanese nationals. This downgrades migrant workers' rights and reframes the issue as one of protecting nationals.⁴⁹

Equity: Where Law Meets Public Health

Text take from report by Swarup Sarkar^{50 51}

Ensuring equity in service delivery is essential. Continuous access to essential health and social services must be maintained for all populations, including migrants, informal workers, and marginalized groups, irrespective of their legal status. Services should be designed to ensure accessibility, availability, and acceptability, particularly for those with limited options.

Gender-sensitive approaches must be integrated into all aspects of epidemic response. Monitoring should go beyond mortality to capture indirect impacts on women and vulnerable groups, including access to services, economic effects, and exposure to violence. Protecting and advancing gender equality must remain a priority.

The European Union has a critical role to play in shaping a rights-based approach to epidemic control in a multipolar world. It should develop common standards for rights-based public health interventions, strengthen cross-border coordination, and ensure that human rights remain central to health governance. The EU can also lead in promoting balanced approaches that integrate human rights, public health evidence, and social considerations.

⁴⁹ Maria Grahn-Farley (2025) 'THE SILENT SOUND OF DROWNING: Human Rights Justifications and Complex Intersectionality', 51 *Brook. J. Int'l L.* 1, 12.

⁵⁰ MD MS, University of Gothenburg, Sweden; Global Health Security Network, Australia; Ex Director/Adviser World Health Organisation, Global Fund, UNAIDS, Asian Development Bank, UNITAID, CARE International; Ex CG Pandit National Chair, Indian Council of Medical Research.

⁵¹ WP 2 Reclaiming Human Rights for Effective Epidemic Control: Lessons from COVID-19 – a suggested policy approach for the EU, Swarup Sarkar, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19865020.

Crisis and its Phases

We have identified that the role of HRJs in connection to crisis can loosely be identified through three phases, and it is in the third phase human rights justifications are more clearly used in the cases we have studied. The first being the crisis itself. However, it seems to depend on when the State determines the situation to be a crisis and that HRJs play a more significant role when the crisis is not as obvious as for example with COVID-19's initial and active stages or in the migration crisis in 2015 when people were arriving in the thousands to Europe. The second is the normalizing phase where values and ideas of normalcy adjust to the conditions of the crisis: this is when the immediate crisis has passed and the new set of values it generated have become part of the "new normal." The third is the institutionalizing phase: this is when the normalized new values have lost their connection to the original crisis and need to be institutionalized in law and this is also where the instruments that were developed for the crisis risk falling into a function creep, to be used for issues unrelated to the original crisis situation.

We have identified through the different studies that the risk of dilution of human rights through HRJs is not - as our original thesis had presumed - happening at the moment of the crisis, but rather in its aftermath, when the crisis has dissipated and the State is in the process of institutionalizing the instruments that were born out of and which had become normalized during the crisis. In other words, it is in the moment of institutionalization that the risk of misuse of human rights through HRJs is heightened. This is also the moment when the risk of function creep seems to be at its greatest, i.e. the application of a measure designed, justified and implemented for one specific purpose to another sphere.

Our research has found that it is in this phase that HRJs have been used with regard to both the migration crisis and to the COVID-19 crisis, but not for climate change.

In a forthcoming article entitled *From Open Hearts to Closed: Legitimizing Weaker Asylum Rights through Human Rights Justifications*, forthcoming in *Juridisk Tidskrift* (2026), Elica Ghavidel and Maria Nääv examine the use of HRJs in a Swedish migration law context. They find that such justifications were employed in Sweden in connection with the institutionalization of a weakening of the right to asylum in 2021. Nääv and Ghavidel show that the use of HRJs was needed in the institutionalization phase, as rights were an integral part of the values that were important to Sweden's self-image. The human right to asylum could successfully be invoked by the Swedish legislator to justify a change in asylum legislation that only a few years earlier had required the existence of a "crisis" in order to be regarded as legitimate. The authors further conclude that, as deployed in the legislative process, the HRJ argument functions to legitimize the curtailment of the right to asylum in Sweden. The institutionalization of temporary residence permits in 2021, in turn, paved the way for subsequent restrictive legislative measures in Swedish asylum and migration law.

The situation is different for climate change, where the crisis in the strict sense might be conceived as yet to come, although the effects of climate change are becoming all too real in many countries, and to some extent at least the State is able to define whether it is a crisis or not. Nonetheless, most States currently avoid or reject a crisis narrative, especially in the context of judicial proceedings – as admitting the existence of a crisis would require more urgent and sweeping measures on their part. However, the same States might recognize climate change as a current or future crisis in other contexts. An important exception is represented by States that are most vulnerable to climate change (especially small island developing States), which consistently use the language of crisis or emergency when referring to climate change. As WP6 primarily focused on litigation, this aspect was not examined in-depth in the context of climate change, and the following considerations refer to the areas of COVID and Migration. Nonetheless, further research would be appropriate on how the same State might assume a different position depending on the context as well as on how the lack of reference to crisis can also be problematic.

Function Creep

The risk of function creep arises when the action has drifted away from its original purpose and is being applied for a separate purpose that was not the focus of the original discussion, debate and scrutiny. To give one example, Sweden used a HRJ that it was following the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child article 19 (to prevent children from being subjected to abuse) in adopting Stop-and-Search zones in social-economically vulnerable migrant communities in the fight against Gangs. The law was heavily critiqued by human rights and child rights organizations for having discriminatory effects from an intersectional perspective against migrant children (mostly boys) living in marginalized and segregated areas. The justification for the adoption of this law was originally that the gangs operate, and crimes take place in migrant areas. However, this same law was later activated by the Swedish police between 7th and 21st April 2026 to protect the Israeli Embassy after significant hostilities commenced between Israel and Iran. Clearly there has been function creep: the area where the Israeli embassy is located is in one of the most affluent areas in Sweden, and the law no longer has any connection to tackling fighting gangs, which was the original purpose and justification for its adoption.⁵²

Another example concerns electronic tracing. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Taiwan adopted the “digital fencing” mechanism, repurposing cell phones and cell towers (which were originally tools and infrastructure that served private communication) for quarantine enforcement. For contact tracing, Taiwan also used cell tower history to retroactively locate cellphones, as proxies of their owners, to map the digital footprint of people confirmed with COVID-19. Again, this demonstrates function creep, where an approach and data use adopted for one reason (private communications) was appropriated for a very different purpose.

⁵² Section 22 b of the Police Statute

Abstract and Concrete Human Rights Justifications

We have found two areas where there is a more significant regulatory gap when HRJs are being used.

First, there is a distinction between when HRJs are applied or used in an abstract application or as a concrete application. Abstract applications include the legislative phase, whereas a concrete application is when the justification is applied within a legal process in the Court.

Further, there is a distinction between when HRJs are used on the horizontal level i.e. as between States, and when they are used in a vertical form i.e. within States. HRJs between States will be more of a political character but even those used on a political horizontal level can, dependent on the national constitutional design, affect whether the political use of a HRJ on the horizontal inter-State level will have legal vertical effects upon the individual rights-holding person.

We have found that it is in the abstract legislative phase that HRJs have the most severe consequences because there is little ability to challenge for example populist agendas with illiberal characteristics done in the name of human rights. This is also the area where the regulatory gap in the human rights regimes is the largest, depending on the strength of the specific country's constitutional design and strength of the judicial review mechanisms in the municipal constitutional order.

The capacity of judicial review to effectively scrutinize the use of HRJs is limited in Sweden, while Finland has a process for some form of review in the legislative phase. The Swedish system includes provision for legislative inquiries which is intended to allow critique from Civil Society, the public authorities and the Courts as well as the Legislative Council when proposing new laws. However, this process has become redundant as the current

government has decided to ignore it. When it comes to Taiwan, a clear limitation is that at the moment it does not have a functioning Constitutional Court but normally with the Court in place the judicial review ex-post has had an effective function. India the ex-post judicial review and the Supreme Court's power to check the legislators' use of human rights justification has also been effective.

Constitutional design matters

This section reports on a number of elements of our research into how a country's constitution impacts on HRJs. As the HRJust consortium members have produced a number of previously produced reports, articles and books generated by the project, the key points are summarized below with citations for the fuller documents.

Text taken from report authored by Hui-Chieh Su, *An Analytical Framework for Assessing the Effectiveness of Judicial Review Against HRJ: to address the gaps in individual human rights protection when States use HRJs*.

To effectively identify and curb governmental HRJs, one must rely on checks and balances exercised by both the legislative and judicial branches. In particular, in parliamentary systems and presidential systems under unified government, the degree of independence courts can maintain in exercising ex ante or ex post judicial review largely determines how far HRJ can spread. This project develops an analytical framework for assessing the capacity of judicial review to counter governmental HRJ, namely:

- At the systemic level of constitutional design, whether courts can detect distortions and abuses of separation-of-powers and checks-and-balances mechanisms (including legislative and administrative procedures) by the government.
- In concrete contexts, whether courts can substantively review the political and legal arguments proposed by the government under the banner of HRJ, and, through rights-

oriented legal interpretations, effectively safeguard the interests of marginalized groups that are underrepresented in the political process.

Another important finding of this project is the identification of patterns in governmental strategies for deploying HRJ. More specifically, the project examines the types of cases in which governments are more or less likely to invoke HRJ, and whether HRJ is used to justify state action or inaction. Beyond systemic factors rooted in constitutional design, three additional variables are relevant here: the scope of the State's duties to protect human rights, the immediacy of the human rights risk, and whether the case concerns marginalized or vulnerable groups that cannot be adequately represented through democratic processes. The Taiwan COVID-measures case demonstrates that, in typical situations involving restrictions on individual negative rights, the government generally does not need to invoke HRJ, as ordinary public-interest justifications suffice to legitimize the State's restrictive actions. Climate litigation, somewhat in between, shows the use by States of both public-interest justifications and HRJs (and related notions) as a response to claims alleging insufficient climate action. The area of climate change is distinctive in that courts tend to allow a wide margin of discretion to the legislative and executive branches in the choice of the best-suited measures to combat climate change, at times even refusing to adjudicate climate-related cases on the merits because of their alleged non-justiciability.

On the other hand, when cases involve marginalized or vulnerable groups that cannot be adequately represented through democratic processes (for example, migrants, refugees, and minors), governments are more inclined to rely on HRJ regardless of whether the rights at issue are framed as negative or positive obligations. In such cases, governments strategically choose between negative-obligation and positive-obligation framings of HRJ as needed. More concretely, when the government seeks to deny the negative rights of members of marginalized groups, it tends to invoke HRJ in a positive obligation register to justify State action that violates negative obligations (for instance, restricting children's personal liberty in the name of protecting the "best interests of the child"). Conversely, when the government wishes to deny the positive rights of marginalized groups, it tends to invoke

HRJ in a negative obligation register to justify State inaction that violates positive obligations (for example, refusing to legislate a minimum wage for migrant workers on the grounds of safeguarding their “freedom of contract”).

When viewed again through the systemic lens of constitutional design, these patterns in governmental HRJ strategies reveal the following: in jurisdictions like Sweden, where judicial review lacks independence, courts will be unable to effectively protect precisely those vulnerable groups most in need of judicial protection when their human rights are curtailed via HRJ. Conversely, in jurisdictions with highly independent courts, the legal system may be able, at a systemic level, to contain HRJ, provided that courts can clearly identify governmental HRJ strategies and respond with robust human rights reasoning and persuasive legal interpretation.

The examples of India, Sweden, and Finland are included here as examples of Constitutional design and how it affects how HRJs can be deployed and also be subjected to review.

India

Authored by Namita Wahi, text from her report, Human Rights Justifications in India.

India has been a liberal constitutional democracy since 1950. As such, it has played a pioneering role in the development of comparative constitutional norms and in supporting the adoption of Human Rights on the international plane in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), and subsequently in the adoption of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights¹⁹⁶⁶ (hereinafter “the ICCPR”) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (hereinafter “the ICESCR”) . Following liberation from British colonial rule, the Republic of India came into existence with the adoption of the Constitution in 1950, The first Constitution of a Commonwealth nation to be drafted completely by its own nationals, the Indian Constitution is the longest written constitution

in the world. Part III of the Constitution guarantees to all citizens Fundamental Rights to life, liberty, equality and property. The Constitution also established a democratic system of government and guaranteed universal adult suffrage to all. As a result, all Indians, irrespective of class, caste, gender, status and ethnicity went overnight from being subjects to citizens.⁵³

The fear of external domination has however been omnipresent in political and cultural discourse. Centuries of British colonial rule and the task upon the new Indian nation to integrate 526 princely states with British India, especially with hostile neighbours, China and Pakistan on its borders (India went on to fight wars with both), has meant that until 1991 India always sought to reduce reliance upon foreign powers.⁵⁴ For instance, as the world entered into a Cold War phase between the U.S. and U.S.S.R., India's first PM Nehru cofounded the non-aligned movement, maintaining a near equal distance from both powers.⁵⁵

Within the domestic constitutional context, some human rights are guaranteed to citizens and aliens (both legal and illegal) whereas some are restricted only to citizens. For instance, in the context of the 1950 Indian Constitution, the right to life and personal liberty and protection against arbitrary arrest is available to both citizens and aliens (Article 21), but the rights to freedom of movement, livelihood, speech and expression are available only to citizens (Article 19).⁵⁶

⁵³ Constitution of India, 1950 (as amended). For background on the drafting process, see Granville Austin, *The Indian Constitution: Cornerstone of a Nation* (Oxford University Press, 1966). On universal adult suffrage, see Art. 326 of the Constitution.

⁵⁴ On the integration of princely states, see V.P. Menon, *The Story of the Integration of the Indian States* (Orient Longman, 1956). On India's wars with China (1962) and Pakistan (1947, 1965, 1971), see Srinath Raghavan, *War and Peace in Modern India* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2010).

⁵⁵ On the Non-Aligned Movement and India's role, see Vijay Prashad, *The Darker Nations: A People's History of the Third World* (New Press, 2008); Jawaharlal Nehru, *The Discovery of India* (Oxford University Press, 1989 [1946]). The First Conference of Heads of State or Government of Non-Aligned Countries was held in Belgrade in 1961.

⁵⁶ Constitution of India 1950, Art. 21 (right to life and personal liberty, available to all persons); Art. 22 (protection against arbitrary arrest); Art. 19 (freedoms of speech, movement, and livelihood, available to citizens only). See also *A.K. Gopalan v. State of Madras*, AIR 1950 SC 27, and the subsequent evolution of Art. 21 jurisprudence in *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*, AIR 1978 SC 597.

The Constitution of India has been amended more than a hundred times and the Fundamental Right to Property was abolished in 1978.⁵⁷ Nevertheless, in its continuing democratic form of government and the fundamental rights guarantees of life, liberty, and equality, despite periods of authoritarian rule, it has arguably remained a liberal constitutional democracy over the past 75 years.

Ever since it emerged as an independent nation, India's position on human rights on the international plane has been shaped by the political leadership's deep commitment to human rights coupled with the fear of external domination. The demand for basic civil and political rights had formed the basis of India's freedom struggle. A decade after the establishment of the Indian National Congress (the "Congress"), in 1895, the Constitution of India Bill (also known as the Home Rule Bill) had sought certain constitutionally guaranteed rights for the first time, *inter alia*, the freedom of expression, inviolability of one's house, right to property and equality before the law, all of which were rights recognised under British common and statutory law in England. Decades later, the Commonwealth of India Bill, 1925, envisaged a "statement of rights" including the right to property. A series of events including the British colonial government's failure to respond to these demands for fundamental rights, and the arrival of Mahatma Gandhi in India and his success in leading the Indian National Congress from being merely the domain of upper-class intelligentsia and landed classes into a genuine mass movement, converted these demands for fundamental rights into a demand for *purna swaraj* or complete freedom from British rule. Post independence, India played a key role in the Non-Aligned Movement and led the developing world in its articulation of civil and political, and economic, social and cultural rights in the UDHR, ICCPR and ICESCR.

The Right to Development (RtD) has been used as a justification across a range of contexts — from diplomatic negotiations and UN treaty processes to domestic policy debates and domestic courts. Within the domestic context, there is often differential use of the RtD by both the executive and the judiciary. There is considerable evidence for the use of HRJs by

⁵⁷ Forty Fourth Constitutional Amendment, 1978

various agencies and bodies of the executive branch of the government in both domestic and international policy.

In India, the RtD is utilized by the Indian executive in both domestic and international fora as inextricably interlinked with the idea of nationhood, and national interest, and hence related to the right to self-determination. The juridification of the “Right to Development” by the Indian judiciary derives largely from parts III and IV of the Constitution, that correspond to Fundamental Rights and Directive Principles of State Policy. In this context, the “Right to Development” is derived from the “Right to Life” enshrined in Article 21 of the Constitution.⁵⁸

Sweden

Authored by Martin Westlund, text partly taken from his report, *Judicial Review in Sweden in the Context of Migration Law: Control Mechanisms and Human Rights Challenges*

How HRJs can be reviewed depends on constitutional design, for instance the form and scope of judicial review. Where courts have limited powers to strike down or review legislative choices, HRJs are less likely to be subjected to meaningful scrutiny. In such systems, such as Sweden, human rights concerns are addressed primarily within the political process. While judicial review is formally available, it rarely entails a deep substantive assessment of legislative choices. In the EU context, the CJEU has the competence to review and invalidate legal acts, but still often exercises restraint in politically sensitive areas, which limits the intensity of review in practice. Where courts both can and are willing to engage in substantive review, judicial review can function as a constraint on the use of HRJs by requiring governments to justify their claims through rights-based reasoning. The form and intensity of judicial review are thus decisive factors in determining whether the use and potential impacts of HRJs are contained.

⁵⁸ See *Samatha v. State of Andhra Pradesh*, (1997) 8 SCC 191; *Narmada Bachao Andolan v. Union of India*, AIR 2000 SC 3751. The Directive Principles of State Policy (Part IV, Arts. 36–51) guide the state towards securing socio-economic rights, and the Supreme Court has read several of these into Art. 21 via the “right to life”. See also *Olga Tellis v. Bombay Municipal Corporation*, AIR 1986 SC 180 (right to livelihood as part of Art. 21).

Swedish institutional design - particularly with regard to judicial review - has been examined by postdoctoral researcher Maria Nääv in an article entitled *Lagrådsgranskningen i reformernas tid* (English: *Judicial Review by the Council on Legislation in an Era of Reform*), forthcoming in *Förvaltningsrättslig tidskrift* (2026). The article analyses how the legislature has responded, in a number of legislative processes, to observations made by the Council on Legislation (Lagrådet) - the Swedish body entrusted with ex-ante constitutional review of proposed legislation concerning non-compliance with human rights norms. Nääv finds that the legislature, as a general rule, does not adhere to the Council's objections regarding the compatibility of proposed legislation with human rights. Instead, it tends to display greater fidelity to the Tidö Agreement concluded between the governing parties and the immigration-critical party Sweden Democrats prior to the current electoral term. This is explained by the fact that the Tidö Agreement is existentially significant for the government's continued tenure in office. The study thus exposes structural weaknesses in Swedish institutional design in relation to judicial review when it comes to proposed legislation concerning non-compliance with human rights norms.

Finland

During the pandemic, Finland relied on Section 23 of the Finnish Constitution, entitled 'Basic rights and liberties in situations of emergency', as well as on the Emergency Powers Act, which constitutes a parallel source for emergency powers and codifies the more detailed provisions on the use of emergency powers. Both were put into operation for the first time during the pandemic. In contrast to Sweden, the mention of emergency in the Constitution as well as the existence of an emergency law enabled Finland to rely on emergency powers already prescribed in law.

Constitutional design dependent on topic: Climate Change

The Constitutional design is not only related to the specific constitutional jurisdiction but can also be approached from the perspective of the climate crisis spanning a variety of jurisdictions.

This text is based on Chiara Tea Antoniazzi, *Report on Climate-Related Litigation and the Separation of Powers*, last updated January 2026.

In the area of climate change, as mentioned above, courts generally show significant deference towards legislative and executive bodies.⁵⁹ Nonetheless, the principle of the separation of powers is interpreted differently from country to country and has led to a variety of judicial approaches. Accordingly, decisions range from the *Leghari* case (in relation to which the Lahore High Court ordered detailed measures to the executive); to the *Urgenda* case, where the Dutch Supreme Court ordered emissions reduction by a specific amount but left the government ample discretion in the choice of means to attain that objective; to the case *Klimaseniorinnen and Others v. Switzerland*, where the European Court of Human Rights did not specify the result either; to multiple instances where the courts rejected the cases as inadmissible in light of the principle of the separation of powers and the so-called political question doctrine (e.g.: the *Aurora* case in Sweden; the *A Sud et al.* case in Italy; the *People v. Arctic Oil* case in Norway; and the *La Rose et al.* case in Canada).

Constitutional design dependent on topic: Pandemic Preparedness

From text written by Swarup Sarkar^{60 61}

Public health interventions should be calibrated, proportionate, and evidence based. Uniform, large-scale coercive measures should be replaced with context-specific strategies informed by epidemiological data and local conditions. Greater emphasis should be placed

⁵⁹ This paragraph concerning litigation in the area of climate change is based on Chiara Tea Antoniazzi, *Report on Climate-Related Litigation and the Separation of Powers*, last updated January 2026.

⁶⁰ MD MS, University of Gothenburg, Sweden; Global Health Security Network, Australia; Ex Director/Adviser World Health Organisation, Global Fund, UNAIDS, Asian Development Bank, UNITAID, CARE International; Ex CG Pandit National Chair, Indian Council of Medical Research.

⁶¹ WP 2 Reclaiming Human Rights for Effective Epidemic Control: Lessons from COVID-19 – a suggested policy approach for the EU, Swarup Sarkar, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19865020.

on early detection, community engagement, and targeted interventions that minimize disruption while maintaining effectiveness.

The Role of Civil Society and Human Rights Defenders in Upholding Multilateralism and Holding the Government Accountable when using Human Rights Justifications

Sweden's system for a formalized process for the engagement between government and Civil Society is currently not operating as intended, as the existing government is choosing to ignore it, as discussed by Maria Nääv in an article entitled *Lagrådsgranskningen i reformernas tid* (English: *Judicial Review by the Council on Legislation in an Era of Reform*), forthcoming in *Förvaltningsrättslig tidskrift* (2026). The article analyses how the legislature has responded, in a number of legislative processes, to observations made by the Council on Legislation (Lagrådet) and in a report entitled *A Report on How Human Rights Organisations Respond to the Use of Human Rights Justifications in Swedish legislative preparatory works*, by Haidar Al-Amirtaha and Maria Nääv.

Haidar Al-Amirthaha and Maria Nääv examine two public legislative inquiries, Ds 2024:30 and SOU 2024:93, to study the ways in which Swedish legislative inquiries invoke human rights, primarily the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the European Convention on Human Rights, as Human Rights Justifications (HRJs), to justify their legislative proposals. They consider how Civil Society in the shape of human rights organisations responds in the consultation processes when the State uses HRJs to justify its decisions. The results show that human rights organisations require resource-intensive legal expertise to respond to the rights arguments which the State uses. Given the challenges such organisations face in securing this expertise, this increases the risk that the organisations may not have the legal

capacity to respond with the corresponding rights-based arguments used by the legislator and therefore that criticism of these legislative proposals instead falls back on user/interest- and needs-based arguments. This, in turn, risks shifting the deliberative democratic dialogue on the legislative proposals (which entail restrictions of rights) from a question of whether the State has legally based obligations and individuals have rights under the law, to whether individuals have interests or needs that the State may choose to address or not.

Community Engagement as a Core Component of Epidemic Response: a public health perspective

Community engagement must be institutionalized as a core component of epidemic preparedness and response. Organisations representing people with lived experience play a crucial role in bridging the gap between the State and affected populations. They act as buffers that can absorb human rights shocks, ensure access to services, and enhance trust. Their involvement should extend beyond observation to active participation in policy formulation, service design, and programme implementation well before any epidemic hits.

A Model developed by HRJust for how to Reinvigorate Civil Society - Rings on Water (RoW) through Democratic Inclusion

This section is taken from the D 7.5 Inclusive Democracy and Intersectionality authored by Yu-Ling Huang

In order to understand these issues in more detail, an integral part of the HRJust project has been innovative and effective engagement with Civil Society. The “Rings on Water” (RoW) methodology was developed within the project as a replicable approach to sustained co-production between academia and Civil Society. It emerged in response to a broader contraction of meaningful Civil Society engagement within liberal democratic contexts. In

Sweden, formal consultation mechanisms have been streamlined and funding for Civil Society reduced. In Taiwan, pandemic-era emergency governance revealed the limits of procedural rights protections in a relatively young democracy. In both settings, RoW provided a participatory framework where existing democratic channels had either weakened or were not yet fully institutionalized.

The methodology unfolds through a series of expanding “rings,” each building on a prior stage. It begins with a small, carefully selected group - such as judicial actors, representatives from national human rights institutions and senior NGO leaders - who collaboratively define core concepts and identify key knowledge gaps. Subsequent stages bring in additional sectors, regions and perspectives, extending the process while drawing on the trust and shared language developed earlier. Each ring is guided by three aims: to produce knowledge that no single actor could generate independently; to develop policy insights through structured cross-sector dialogue; and to establish new networks and alliances across institutional boundaries.

When Human Rights Defenders are Targeted: a gap in EU Horizon Reporting System

There are clear limitations on thinking that human rights defenders and Civil Society will have the resources or the protection needed to defend human rights alone without the support of a benevolent liberal democratic State. It becomes not only difficult but dangerous when the State becomes an active opponent to Civil Society’s human rights commitments. Below is one such example.

Concerns about the security of our researchers and the human rights defenders we have encountered and worked with throughout this project highlight a serious gap in the EU Horizon reporting system.

HRJust explores how States use and misuse arguments about human rights to justify and defend their policies and actions (the Human Rights Justifications or HRJs of our title).

Inevitably, therefore, HRJust is identifying sensitive issues, issues that are intended to be shared with EU because they affect the research that can be done and its methodology and workflows. As a result, the risks to our researchers and to the Civil Society members and groups we have engaged with has been a constant, ever-present concern to us throughout the project. Nonetheless, we have been determined to fulfil our brief and ensure that EU is aware of the issues we are exploring and their implications, while still maintaining the highest level of scientific security and reliability of the data collected and the research results presented.

Through this, we have identified a worrying gap in the EU Horizon reporting regime. At present, there is no safe way or method within the EU reporting system for anyone at risk to share their research results when these might be critical of the State for example. This presents a serious threat to academic freedom and democratic Civil Society.

Horizon researchers report their findings via SyGMA, a report system to which every researcher in the project and all the administrators from each beneficiary have access. This means SyGMA is not a safe or secure reporting venue for researchers under threat because it means one researcher is putting their safety in the hands of a large group of people, because everyone can access and download that data, even if what is submitted through SyGMA is later classified as Sensitive. Obviously, there are good reasons for this ability to access others' information - for instance, some of our researchers have generated foundational data for understanding a specific research outcome which is important in informing other researchers. The fact that Horizon does not have a safe alternative for a researcher to report their findings raises the risks that it will not be possible to conduct or share research that is important for EU in understanding its role and guiding its policies when it comes to democracy and human rights.

This is a system that EU must reconsider and reform if it is to remain possible to conduct research on democracy and human rights in the areas and on the topics that are under the heaviest attack from authoritarianism.

The attacks on research, researchers and human rights defenders are not limited to specific regions and can take place in the most unexpected places. The difference is that in some places, it is still safe to report on these attacks by the State.

We have encountered a number of examples of where States have and are acting to stifle research and reporting. We have taken the decision not to detail these in order to protect those involved. However, in order to provide an illustration, we are including an example from Sweden, where we consider it safe to do so, even though human rights organizations are reporting an increasingly hostile State and where funding is being used as means of influencing human rights organizations from critiquing the State. We would argue that the following example shows the negative way in which a member of the Swedish government has acted towards our project and also towards human rights defenders in Sweden when they critique the government on human rights grounds.

As project Coordinator, I presented the findings from our project about how the Swedish Government is using human rights justifications in bad faith when proposing a law where children can be forced to wear electronic monitoring bracelets (against their own and their parents' consent) for having been disrespectful to teachers or their parents. This law is explicitly stated to be applied in migrant areas, in other words affecting migrant children the most and risks having discriminatory effects on whole groups of people. In addition, it entails using a criminal sanction (which being forced to wear an electronic monitoring bracelet is) for a non-criminal action – it is not a crime to be disrespectful towards your teacher or your parents. It is a violation of fundamental human rights principles to use criminal sanctions for non-criminal acts. The government has used a HRJ to defend this law, arguing that it was in the best interest of the child (art. 3 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child - CRC), and to protect the child from abuse (art. 19 of the CRC).

This talk was presented to the Queen of Sweden, Silvia and the Minister of Social Services (the Minister responsible for this legislative proposal), Camilla Waltersson Grönwall. After the talk, the Minister came up to me and declared that I had no right to give that talk in front

of the Queen, that it was a shame upon myself and an insult to the Queen to present a human rights critique in this setting.

Not only is this clearly inappropriate in a democracy, but it does also illustrate that many in government do not wish their decisions and their underpinning reasoning to be scrutinized in public. It should be stressed that the human rights attacks and the pressure faced by some of our researchers and some of the human rights organizations we have worked with in this project are far worse but we include this as an example, and would suggest that it is not difficult to consider how a similar act and reaction might play out in a State other than Sweden. Not only have we faced issues with the research itself, but we have heard from participants of the climate of obstruction and fear that States can generate in order to shut down public criticism. This makes it even more important the EU's systems enable confidential reporting, which should of course include the evidence to substantiate any statements being made.

The existing Horizon and SyGMA systems do not offer secure ways of reporting sensitive research. The relationship between safety and importance of the research is inverse when it comes to research on democracy and human rights. The most important human rights violations to report also becomes the most dangerous to write about; the greater the risk and the consequences, then, the more dangerous is it to report this and also to explain how the culture and politics of threat against researchers and human rights defenders shapes the whole research culture and the whole democratic environment in which the research can take place. Without a change, EU risks not becoming fully informed of the issues that it has commissioned researchers to identify and report and therefore risks its policies and actions falling short of what is required to fulfil EU's objectives.

The connection between a Geopolitical and a municipal political context

Ukraine

Text drawn from: Olena Chernenko & Martin Westlund, *Why the Temporary Protection Directive Was Activated: Solidarity, Geopolitics, and Humanitarian Considerations*, 2 *Europa Rättslig Tidskrift (ERT)* (2026).

As set out above, an understanding why the EU acted so decisively in 2022 requires examining Ukraine's long-standing integration into the European legal and political space. This section considers some of the specific issues about the connection between geopolitical and the municipal political context in more detail. The TPD's activation was the culmination of decades of integration that made Ukraine appear as part of the European community. Ukraine is more than an external neighbor, and this shows in the EU's response. Activating the TPD was also a geopolitical act. The EU framed temporary protection as an expression of solidarity with Ukraine, aligning its migration response with its broader foreign policy objectives.

Ukraine's gradual integration into the European legal and political community began early in its independence, through constitutional and legislative declarations affirming its participation in the 'pan-European process'. Over time, Ukraine has become increasingly close to the EU, demonstrated by the country's visa-free regime,⁶² and its association agreements.⁶³ These legal milestones strengthen the perception that Ukraine belongs to Europe's political sphere.

Ukraine signaled its European aspirations early. The 1990 Declaration of State Sovereignty affirmed Ukraine's participation in the "pan-European process and European structures".⁶⁴ The 1993 Verkhovna Rada decision declared that Ukrainian membership in the European

⁶² Regulation (EU) 2017/850 (Ukraine visa exemption).

⁶³ Association Agreement between the European Union and Its Member States, of the one part, and Ukraine, of the other part. Document 22014A0529(01).

⁶⁴ Declaration of State Sovereignty of Ukraine', 16 July 1990, No 55-XII.

Community was the long-term goal of foreign policy, outlining steps toward a Partnership and Cooperation Agreement as the first step toward association and eventual membership.⁶⁵ By 2010, the Law ‘On the Principles of Domestic and Foreign Policy’ explicitly defined ‘ensuring Ukraine’s integration into the European political, economic and legal space with the aim of acquiring membership in the European Union’ as a principle of foreign policy.⁶⁶ The Constitution affirms ‘the European identity of the Ukrainian people and the irreversibility of Ukraine's European and Euro-Atlantic course’.⁶⁷ These constitutional provisions and legislative acts anchor Ukraine’s aspirations to become part of the European political and legal space, demonstrating Ukraine’s constitutional self-identification with Europe.

The EU confirmed Ukraine’s belonging through key steps. In 2014, the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement aimed to promote gradual rapprochement based on shared values, enhanced political dialogue, regional peace, and progressive integration into the EU’s internal market.⁶⁸ The Agreement stressed that respect for democratic principles, human rights, sovereignty, and territorial integrity constitute ‘essential elements’ of the EU-Ukraine relationship. In 2017, Ukrainian citizens were granted visa-free travel to the EU for short stays – presented as a symbol of trust and Ukraine’s anchoring in the European community.⁶⁹ When the EU activated the TPD in 2022, it explicitly highlighted this visa-free regime as justification. Temporary protection thus continues Ukraine’s gradual integration.

The decision was also framed in geopolitical terms. The Council and the Commission emphasized Ukraine’s visa-free status and ties under the Association Agreement as evidence of a privileged partnership. They presented the TPD as an act of solidarity with

⁶⁵ Resolution of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, ‘On the Main Directions of Ukraine’s Foreign Policy’, 2 July 1993.

⁶⁶ Law of Ukraine, ‘On the Principles of Domestic and Foreign Policy’, 1 July 2010, No 2411-VI (Revision of 2010); Law of Ukraine, ‘On National Security of Ukraine’, 21 June 2018, No 2469-VIII.

⁶⁷ Paragraph 5 of the preamble, Constitution of Ukraine, as amended by Law No. 2680-VIII of 07.02.2019

⁶⁸ EU-Ukraine Association Agreement.

⁶⁹ Regulation (EU) 2017(850 (Ukraine visa exemption).

Ukraine as a European partner. The Association Agreement and visa liberalization are instruments of differentiated integration, embedding Ukraine within the EU's normative and economic order without formal membership.⁷⁰ Such agreements are often described as mechanisms of 'external governance' or 'integration without membership', reinforcing geopolitical proximity and shared identity.⁷¹ Temporary protection represents a further step in consolidating Ukraine's embeddedness within the European legal space. Russia's aggression was framed not only as a direct threat to Ukraine's sovereignty, but also as a challenge to EU values, stability, and security. The activation thus served a dual purpose: to manage displacement and to signal geopolitical loyalty.

The EU's portrayal of solidarity cannot be detached from questions of identity and belonging. As Ursula von der Leyen, the Commission President, expressed shortly after the invasion: 'they belong to us. They are one of us and we want them in'.⁷² This framing reflects political alignment and cultural closeness. Sociologically, empathy and solidarity are more easily extended when two groups perceive themselves as sharing similar norms and values.⁷³ This perspective helps explain the more positive reception of Ukrainians compared to those arriving from the Middle East and North Africa in 2015. When an 'out-group' is perceived as holding different values or norms, it can be constructed as a threat to collective identity and reinforce exclusionary policies.⁷⁴ Media coverage of Ukrainians has generally been positive,

⁷⁰ Frank Schimmelfennig, 'Differentiated Integration in the European Union' (2018) 25 *European Union Politics* 115; Katarzyna Wolczuk, 'Ukraine and the EU: Turning the Association Agreement into a Success Story' (2014) 56 *European Policy Centre Policy Brief*.

⁷¹ Sandra Lavenex, 'EU External Governance in: "Wider Europe"' (2004) 11 *Journal of European Public Policy*; Frank Schimmelfennig, Dirk Leuffen and Berthold Rittberger, *Differentiated Integration: Explaining Variation in the European Union* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2013); Andrew Geddes, *Migration as Foreign Policy? Europe and Beyond* (Report, Fundação Getúlio Vargas 2019).

⁷² Méabh Mc Mahon, 'Ukraine is one of us and we want them in the EU, Ursula von der Leyen tells Euronews' *Euronews* (27 February 2022) <https://www.euronews.com/2022/02/27/ukraine-is-one-of-us-and-we-want-them-in-eu-ursula-von-der-leyen-tells-euronews> accessed 5 October 2025.

⁷³ David de Coninck, 'The Refugee Paradox during Wartime in Europe: How Ukrainian and Afghan Refugees are (not) alike' (2023) 57 *The International Migration Review* 582.

⁷⁴ Claudia Postelnicescu, 'Europe's New Identity: The Refugee Crisis and the Rise of Nationalism' (2016) 12 *Europe's Journal of Psychology* 209; Silke Goubin, Anna Ruelens, and Ides Nicaise, 'Trends in Attitudes on Migration in Europe: A Comparative Analysis' HIVA – Research Institute for Work and Society.

emphasizing the human dimension of displacement, individual suffering and resilience, whereas reporting on Syrian refugees centered on scenes of chaos and disorder.⁷⁵

The discourse surrounding Ukraine in 2022 positioned the country as part of Europe's moral and geopolitical sphere. EU officials explicitly described Ukrainians as people who must be protected from Russia's aggression, grounded in the view that they are 'part of us'.⁷⁶ Cultural and civilizational discourse shows how the TPD activation reflects European self-identity. Solidarity functions less as a universal principle of human rights and more as a selective practice of inclusion, applied to those seen as belonging to the European sphere. It functions as boundary-drawing, delineating the contours of European responsibility.

Ukraine's European integration created the foundation for exceptional solidarity, facilitating the Council's decision to activate the TPD. The activation was situated within the broader the EU's broader foreign policy stance and illustrated how migration governance is entwined with the EU's geopolitical response to the war. By granting swift and harmonized protection, the EU reinforced political support. It was a symbolic reaffirmation of Ukraine's place in Europe. Temporary protection thus functions as a legal mechanism of belonging that operates at the intersection of humanitarian law, migration policy, and foreign policy. The TPD activation reveals how migration governance can serve as an instrument of geopolitical positioning, blurring the boundaries between humanitarian response and strategic alliance-building.

Taiwan

The following section is a summary of WP4 Taiwan's final report (Memo 3 on political context).

⁷⁵ Lenka Dražanová and Andrew Geddes, 'Attitudes towards Ukrainian Refugees and Governmental Responses in 8 European Countries' in Sergio Carrera and Meltem Ineli Ciger (eds.) *EU Responses to the Large-Scale Refugee Displacement from Ukraine* (Migration Policy Centre, 2023) 137.

⁷⁶ Giselle Bosse (2022) 546.

The ROC on Taiwan has been excluded from the UN system and the human rights regime due to its non-member status in the United Nations since 1971, when it lost the seat of China to the People's Republic of China (PRC). Since then, Taiwan has been unable to join most international organizations as an official member and lacks access to the Universal Periodic Review (UPR) that seeks to ensure compliance with the UN's conventions. In response to this plight, Taiwan incorporates international human rights treaties into its domestic laws and has established an alternative mechanism for periodic review.

At the outset of the COVID-19 pandemic, Taiwan had just completed its 2020 presidential and legislative elections. In response to the potential threat from China, exemplified in the preceding months in Hong Kong, Taiwan elected a unified government led by a party that has been adopting a more cautious stance toward China, and which was more willing to implement stringent pandemic measures. Some of the measures adopted by the Taiwan Government were criticized for lack of legal authorization or being overbroad in their scope. Yet, under the unified government, Congressional checks and balances were largely inactive. Due to high social pressure, as well as the judiciary's constant deferral to administrative discretion, litigation was also seldom initiated.

After the pandemic subsided, Taiwan completed a new round of presidential and legislative elections in 2024, leading to a divided government. A coalition congressional majority is led by the major opposition party that seeks a closer tie with China. This coalition has not only blocked bills and budget plans proposed by the government, but also enacted laws to paralyze the function of the Constitutional Court, a major avenue for addressing human rights violations. As the growing tension in geopolitics intersects with domestic political divide, congressional checks and balances can easily be hijacked and used as a stage for political showdowns, rather than a mechanism of oversight. It should be noted that the differences between political parties in Taiwan often come down to the divergence on the question of Taiwan's relationship with China. Therefore, the priority of "checks and balances" between political branches is often not about ensuring a well-functioning

mechanism that protects human rights, but about Taiwan's China policy, which can be played out in various forms.

With hindsight, it would be fair to say the unified government that came to power in 2020 allowed Taiwan to navigate smoothly through the early days of the pandemic. Nevertheless, as the pandemic progressed, the excessive measures during the prolonged zero-COVID period also raised concerns about violations of individual rights and other usual perils associated with the concentration of power. Nevertheless, had the 2020 election resulted in a divided government like the current one, Taiwan's COVID-19 pandemic trajectory is likely to have been considerably more chaotic from the onset. This analysis reminds us that pandemic policies were contingent on the larger political context. However, the gains were not without their human costs.

With or without a pandemic like COVID-19, Taiwan's liberal-leaning voters often face the impossible choice between a unified government that is more cautious about China but with weak oversight, and a divided government with a major opposition party that may be willing to play into the hands of its aggressive neighbor. With the growing geopolitical tension, the second option risks allowing the political deadlock to weaken not only the long-fought for human rights mechanism but also the normal functioning of the State. Yet, the first option further risks endorsing the prioritization of security over all other issues, the danger of which was shown during the pandemic.

India

This section is authored by Maria Grahn-Farley

India's recent political context has been characterized by the government's focus on driving development without fully taking into consideration its impact on human rights of those communities most directly affected.

Finland

Comments authored by Milka Surmonen

Geopolitical considerations were not prominent in the COVID-19-related HRJs used by Finland. COVID-policies of other Nordic countries were at times used as a reference when justifying policy choices. In policy making in general, other Nordic countries often form the reference group with which Finland compares itself. For example, in its necessity assessment concerning the lockdown proposal that the Finnish Constitutional Law Committee considered unconstitutional, the Committee gave significance to the fact that other Nordic countries had not imposed similar limitations on freedom of movement. This seems to be the first occasion that the Committee has given weight to this kind of comparative argument in its review of constitutionality.

Sweden

The political context concerning Children (boys) with Migrant Backgrounds

Authored by Maria Grahn-Farley taken from: Maria Grahn-Farley, *The Silent Sound of Drowning: Human Rights Justifications and Complex Intersectionality*, 51 *Brooklyn Journal of International Law* (2025).

When the HRJust project commenced, Swedish politics was dominated by a fear of the extreme right. However, this concern has begun to dissipate from being a mainstream concern and the agenda of the extreme right has become normalized. The extreme-right political party Swedish Democrats, with its origins in the 1980's neo-Nazis movement, has become an accepted political party. Until the election in 2022, it was considered a neutral political position to hold and, today it no longer appears to be a necessary object to address the fact that their political positions are outside of liberal democracy. Currently, the Swedish Democrats are not permitted to participate in the government because of these neo-Nazi origins, despite being the second largest political party. This position is now changing, with the Conservative Party and the Liberal Party having both stated that at the next election in

September 2026 the Swedish Democrats will be allowed into the government and will be given the ministerial position responsible for migration and migrants.

In 2022, the minority Conservative government entered into an agreement (the Tidö-agreement) with the Swedish Democrats in exchange for their support in parliament. As a result, we can see the influence of Swedish Democrats' policies. All the laws addressing migration in Sweden and where HRJs have been used to justify the infringement and derogations of individual human rights of children, especially boys with migrant backgrounds and migrants in general are laws that stem from the Tidö-agreement. This demonstrates the direct connection between the ways HRJs have been used in Sweden with the ideology of a specific political party, for instance the use of HRJs underpinning legislative proposals in the war against gangs that focus on migrant children, especially boys and children with migrant backgrounds, where the use of HRJs appears to be aimed at making the laws seem less severe and less punitive. All these laws are tracked on the home web page of the Swedish Democrats where they are labeled as "completed" or "ongoing" as part of the fulfilling of the Tidö-agreement.⁷⁷ There are public ties between the Swedish Democrats and the extreme-right both in Hungary (Orban until the recent election) and Trumpism, as well a shift in relation to Israel, after having been banned from any diplomatic exchanges from the Israeli side as late as 2024 when the party leader went to Israel without being granted any official meetings with representatives of the Israeli government.⁷⁸ The sentiments in Israel over the Swedish Democrats have changed in two years. The Swedish Democrat was greeted warmly as a speaker invited by the Israeli Minister of Diaspora, Mr. Amichai Chikli at the International Conference at Combatting Anti-Semitism, in January 2026. The relationship towards Russia and Putin has shifted over time towards a more critical position especially after the Russian invasion of Ukraine and Russia's geopolitical proximity to Sweden. The Russian threat has been considered enough for Sweden to abandon its position of neutrality and to join NATO.

⁷⁷ <https://www.sd.se/tidoavtalet/>

⁷⁸ Åkesson is pleased with his Israel trip - but the country rejects SD (The Swedish democrats) (translation by author), Karin Thurfjell, SvD 2nd of Feb 2024 <https://www.svd.se/a/0Q59GA/jimmie-akesson-traffade-ministrar-i-israel-fick-ett-gott-mottagande>

What role geopolitics plays in strategy, resources and reach

India, Ukraine and Taiwan have a different perspective on the post-Cold War rule-based World Order than that of EU and European Member States, with the latter perceiving a withering away of this order. Neither Taiwan nor Ukraine have seen what Europeans have taken for granted as a rule-based multilateral World Order as being fully as rule-based nor as multilateral. For both these countries, they themselves had to take active steps to make themselves part of a multilateral rule-based human rights order - steps that demanded much more from Taiwan and Ukraine than from EU Member States because liberal democracy and the attitude to human rights had been longer established in Europe and because power (force and enforcement) was held by the West. Taiwan and Ukraine made active and conscious decisions to join value-based multilateral regimes as part of their national interests, and they had done so by developing their own methods of creating an interdependency between their State and a multilateral human rights order and through this demonstrating how countries that want to preserve multilateralism must become active and conscious in their decisions and actions in contributing to a multilateral human rights order. The lessons and methods developed by Taiwan and Ukraine through a place-based historicity might inform the EU and Europe at large how to maintain multilateralism through this transitional period, until the relationship between multilateralism and multipolarity becomes more stable.

What our results demonstrate is that the Post Cold War-World Order that EU and the West thought existed at least since the end of the Cold War was not actually as universal as they had assumed. Whilst the European perspective was of a “Cold” War, some other parts of the world were experiencing a much “hotter” war. For instance, Taiwan was living through the White Terror dictatorship between 1949 and 1992 and in India there were emergency laws in place between 1975 and 1977. Ukraine’s independence took place in

1991 and its association with a European identity was inscribed in the first Constitution. In all of these cases, the country has had to battle to gain the types of freedoms that European States have experienced for much longer and seen as almost inevitable. There are lessons for EU Member States and the EU itself to learn from Ukraine, Taiwan and India when understanding the driving force behind a country's and its people's decision to strive for liberal democracy and human rights as part of its identity and its legal system. For instance, Sweden and Finland have been active human rights advocates internationally since the founding of the United Nations, and both countries have experienced relative political and democratic stability during this whole time. Until recently, Sweden has maintained a significant distinction between international human rights and domestic rights. Each country's specific history has clearly shaped how these countries today relate to individual rights and international human rights, and by extension, Human Rights Justifications. We explore this in more detail below.

Although EU countries may differ in their historical context from countries like Ukraine (not currently a full EU Member State), India and Taiwan, maintaining an emphasis on human rights and providing support to those upholding human rights is indispensable to all countries, both EU Member States and Third Countries, and especially for Civil Society and human rights defenders within countries. We have also found that if the EU is to maintain liberal democratic values, it needs to work with partners such as Ukraine and Taiwanese Civil Society and be sensitive when they relate to human rights defenders and researchers within India for example, where one approach will have a strengthening function in one country and in another create additional vulnerabilities for the human rights defenders in that particular context, in the spirit of a dignified interdependency. One of the easiest ways for the EU to expand on this approach would be to make it easier for Civil Society, Human Rights advocates and scholars from these countries to become full partners in research projects like this EU funded Horizon project. According to our findings, India differs from Taiwan and Ukraine by relying more on an independent approach, less entangled with the multilateral human rights regimes of human rights and instead anchoring its individual rights as grounded in its postcolonial history and liberation from British rule, upheld by the

Constitution and an active Supreme Court but nevertheless it would be a good place to start with modernizing the Horizon program and include third countries not only based on economic development but also dependent on the democratic and human rights considerations.

The rapidly changing geopolitical map – reason to reflect

HRJust has identified the importance of paying careful attention to the global context when it comes to upholding liberal democracy and human rights. The project grew out of the concerns about what was happening to human rights in the Post Cold War World Order, an order that according, to Finland's Alexander Stubb ended with the Russian invasion of Ukraine.^[10]

The design for this project was authored in the UK during the years of 2021 and 2022, during the Global COVID-19 pandemic, and the UK had just begun coming to terms with the meaning and consequences of Brexit. At the time, the changing World Order was an academic observation and its de facto meaning remained unclear. One direct effect from the delays in addressing the implications of Brexit on the UK's involvement with Horizon was that the project had to move from Leeds, UK to Gothenburg, Sweden. In fact, as the project has progressed, the interconnection between HRJs and the global context, and the significance and scale of HRJs has become much clearer. In particular, we have found that the growth of HRJs is partly driven by the changes in geopolitics with States like Sweden taking advantage of a weaker external human rights norm, this is evident in its choice of Human Rights Justifications: it seldom uses HRJs from the European Convention because the final meaning of a human right under the European Convention will be interpreted by the Court, while for example the use of the Child Rights Convention ultimately allows the State to make its own interpretation as long as other States would not band together in a collective action. The UN Committee system with its non-legally binding Concluding Observation only carries weight if they are given to a country where the domestic political context gives it weight.

This context is still changing, although, after the Munich Security Conference 2025 where the United States spoke clearly of its new World Order, a position confirmed in this year's Security Conference 2026, 13-15 February, and the hostilities in the Middle East, we know a bit more what this new World Order looks like. For instance, it has been called a World Order with America as the predator hegemon.⁷⁹ Canadian Prime Minister Mark Carney describes what is taking place as a “rupture” and the Finnish President Alexander Stubb warns about “spheres of influence, chaos, and disorder.”⁸⁰

Whilst we do not know what the final shape will be, it is clear that the EU must play an active part in shaping it.

When we started this project, we saw the world as multipolar between three centers: Russia, the West - comprising Europe (and the USA), and China. We categorized these three centers by how they often presented their normative positions on a geopolitical stage when addressing human rights and international law in general. Russia relied on a historical rewriting as driving its invasion of Ukraine. Europe presented itself as a protector and defender of liberal democracy, and China used a cultural relativist argument as explanation for its view on human rights. Now three year later the understanding of the World Order has moved towards a competing narrative between an idea of spheres of influences where the USA can seek to name Canada as the 51st State of the USA, or where Russia can forbid Ukraine from joining NATO, and where Taiwan's situation risks being seen as a purely “domestic” affair between Taiwan and China.

⁷⁹ Stephen M. Walt, *America the Predatory Hegemon*, Feb 26, 2026, *Foreign Affairs*.

⁸⁰ Alexander Stubb, *The West's Last Chance: How to Build a New Global Order Before It's Too Late*, December 2, 2025, *Foreign Affairs*.

Three Competing Rights Regimes through Five Countries and Three Crises

Four years ago, when drafting this grant proposal, we debated if we should use four circles, where the USA would have its own centre even though the countries we study are not in close proximity to the USA. The thinking was at that time that the USA and the EU were ideologically aligned and would share normative foundations and systems, with their values coinciding.

As the example of Ukraine demonstrates, interdependency is central for maintaining multilateralism. Today, it appears clear that Trump's USA does not share the EU's view on multilateralism. However, as a result of the USA's separating itself from the EU and its values, accentuating a multipolar world order, it is clear that multilateralism can no longer be achieved from one center of power or in only one direction but must be gained through collaborations in multiple places and through a complex web of respectful relationships founded on shared values, reflecting the entwining nature of multilateralism.

The new World Order presents opportunities for EU to work with States that share its values, such as Taiwan, and to some extent India with her postcolonial history, and Ukraine, which has clearly stated its commitment to liberal democratic values from its founding constitution and is an official EU candidate country. Whilst the EU - as the only regional inter-state organization able to maintain and support human rights as a geopolitical actor towards third countries - has a heavier weight to carry in defending a liberal democratic normative foundation on the international stage, it is not alone and can act in cooperation not only with like-minded States but also Civil Society and human rights defenders across the Globe where there are allies that share the same values, EU already serves this

important role in both Taiwan and Ukraine. What this project has found is that the value of this support cannot easily be overstated. In fact, this support by the EU is indispensable for the Taiwanese Civil Society and their defense of human rights.

What will be the EU challenge is how to make sure that this struggle for shared values between the EU and States and even Civil Society is manifested through a mutual respect between the EU, people and countries. To be frank, this has not always been the case. It took Europeans a long time to recognise that the EU's role and interest in the conflict between Ukraine and Russia is not one of one-sided assistance in helping Ukraine defend itself, but it represents a much deeper issue - that of the EU together with Ukraine are protecting their values and a commitment to liberal democracy. In similar ways, when the EU is providing what is indispensable human rights support to Civil Society within countries such as Taiwan, these relationships - based on promoting and protecting shared values - are equally valuable to the EU. At the same time, this support must be made with a careful touch and with a sensitivity and care so that the EU's human rights engagement will not risk alienating or putting the human rights community at heightened risk because of, for example, a history of conciliarism that might make an EU-supported human rights agenda be interpreted as new forms of colonial influences. This is why it is necessary for the EU to be sensitive in its approach when supporting human rights agendas in Third Countries.

We have also found how important it is to maintain an interdependent but still distinct relationship between the two human rights levels, the international and the municipal. There is a value in maintaining a distinction between the international-multilateral regime and the municipal incorporation or transformation of said regime into national legislation. To allow for proper judicial review and for checks on politically driven and even populist use of HRJs. What the experience with both Taiwan and Ukraine, India, but most clearly with Sweden demonstrate is that a distinction between municipal and multilateral regimes is necessary for advancing human rights within the countries. The Swedish example is an important example of what happens when this distinction is not maintained i.e. when the government on its own determines its interpretation and meaning of its international human rights obligations, thus avoiding international obligations. It also demonstrates the

difference between the topics of COVID-19 and migration. HRJs are prominent when it comes to migrants, but less common when it comes to COVID-19 not only in Sweden but also in Finland and Taiwan compared to how frequently HRJs are used with regard to migration.

This comparison of frequency does not mean that the use of HRJs in COVID-19 has not had significant and important impacts as when they have been used, they have been used for the most sweeping measures including Zero-COVID strategies, arguing for the collective right to health. Swarup Sarkar⁸¹ advocates that from a public health perspective, future epidemic responses must begin by reaffirming the primary role of human rights as mechanisms of accountability. Human rights should serve to constrain State power and protect individuals, rather than being used primarily to justify restrictive measures. A clear distinction must be maintained between rights as accountability and rights as justification.

The Geopolitical Effects on Topics

Migration

Authored by Laura Carlson WP 5 Lead

The geopolitics of migration refers to the interplay between migration flows and international political power, concerning how human movement both shapes and is shaped by States' interests, security concerns, and regional or global balances of power. Migration is not only a humanitarian or demographic phenomenon - it is a major focus of political contestation, negotiation, and sometimes conflict among States and other international actors, raising issues about State sovereignty, border control, resource distribution, security and stability. It is a central factor in global and regional politics, and a constitutive element of World Order, not a mere side effect of other political, economic, or military dynamics. Often there is a

⁸¹ WP 2 Reclaiming Human Rights for Effective Epidemic Control: Lessons from COVID-19 – a suggested policy approach for the EU, Swarup Sarkar, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19865020.

tension between security-driven, State-centric approaches to migration and ethical questions of human security and dignity, and humanitarian obligations to protect migrants' and refugees' rights under international law. States and non-state actors can instrumentalize migration by encouraging or obstructing flows to gain diplomatic advantage or to pressure neighboring States - a phenomenon evident, for example, when neighboring governments "weaponize" migration by pushing migrants toward rivals to extract concessions. Migration crises can thus become geopolitical events shaping international relations, such as with the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022.

Geopolitics can be seen as a driving force in the migrant legal regimes found in the three jurisdictions covered by WP5-Migration: the EU, Sweden and Taiwan, all three balancing issues of security, humanity and national/regional identity. Sweden can be seen as the most bound by external influences, as it is, as noted above, a signatory to the key international legal instruments concerning refugees (although not to the Migration Convention), is a founding member of the Council of Europe and has ratified the key instruments, and has been a member of the EU since 1995. Consequently, Sweden has the greatest number of regional and international human rights instruments to which to adhere. Despite this, Sweden has used HRJs widely not to protect the rights of migrants and refugees but to limit them and very consciously. The greatest weight has been given by Sweden to nationality, then security and little regard to humanity. On the other side of the spectrum is the EU and its relationship with Ukraine, where it can be argued that affiliation status and close geographical proximity have aided in the extension of solidarity on a European level and not simply an EU level, arguably giving the greatest weight to humanity and security, as well as a European identity. Taiwan arguably is placing security foremost, identity then humanity as can be traced in the migration HRJs identified in the HRJust project.

COVID-19

Authored by Shun-Ling Chen WP4 co-lead

Taiwan

This section is summarized from WP4 Taiwan's final report (memo 2 on geopolitics)

Due to the unique geopolitical relationship between Taiwan and China, Taiwan's isolated status as a non-member state of the WHO, and its bitter experience with SARS, international political tussles and Taiwan's concerns about its international status played prominent roles in COVID-19 governance in Taiwan.

Border control was one of the prominent examples with clear geopolitical dimensions. Throughout the pandemic, Taiwan maintained heightened border restrictions against China, and the entry bans on Chinese nationals outlasted those on other foreign nationals. These China-specific border controls were widely regarded as having helped Taiwan block the first wave of infection and contributed to its positive reputation in preventing the pandemic.

Against the backdrop of Taiwan's long-standing international isolation, its relatively successful early control of COVID-19 created an opportunity for the government to enhance its international visibility and promote its international status. Due to its prevalent use of digital measures, the Taiwanese government projected its image as a "digital democracy." Within this narrative, Taiwan's trustworthy digital measures were positioned in contrast to authoritarian China's draconian lockdown, reinforcing Taiwan's distinction from China. These technologies were subsequently framed not only as products of government-Civil Society collaboration but also as symbols of a technologically advanced state, thereby securing domestic trust and public support.

However, the implementation of digital measures often involved the secondary use of personal data and arbitrary database linkages without explicit legal basis. The privacy and human rights costs were extremely under-evaluated by the government, and the close collaboration between the government and Civil Society was greatly overstated. From the

perspectives of overburdened groups, such as pilots, front-line medical workers, migrant workers, etc., human rights costs were significantly underestimated and overshadowed by the emphasis on gaining a reputation for a “successful” pandemic policy model. People in these groups often faced social pressure caused by stigmatization, and their fundamental human rights, such as freedom of personal liberty, freedom of movement, right to privacy, property right, freedom of speech, freedom of assembly, and right to vote were disproportionately infringed.

Finland and Sweden

Authored by Milka Sormunen WP4 UoH Co-lead beneficiary

As explained above, geopolitical factors were not prominent in defining Finland’s and Sweden’s COVID-19 approaches. In Finland, COVID-policies of other Nordic countries were at times used as a reference when justifying policy choices. In policymaking in general, other Nordic countries often form the reference group with which Finland compares itself. For example, in its necessity assessment concerning the lockdown proposal that the Finnish Constitutional Law Committee considered unconstitutional, the Committee gave significance to the fact that other Nordic countries had not imposed similar limitations on freedom of movement. This seems to be the first occasion for the Committee to give weight to this kind of comparative arguments in its constitutionality review. Moreover, the fact that Finland has codified emergency situations in its Constitution as well as in the Emergency Powers Act enabled Finland to react more swiftly than Sweden, where emergency situations are not mentioned in the Constitution.

“Right to Development” and Sustainable Development

Authored by Namita Wahi, text from her report, Human Rights Justifications in India

The Right to Development is considered a third generation right within the architecture of international human rights law and represents an effort to synthesize the post-colonial

demand for economic equity, justice, and fairness with the established international framework of civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights. It is premised on the notion that “development” itself is a human right, and that the entire structure of international law must be reshaped to reflect this. There are two identifiable strands of the “right to development” in international law: as a *collective* right of states, and an *individual* right.⁸²

Across both domestic and international contexts, articulation of the “Right to Development” has been tempered by the concept of “sustainable development”. Arising from the notions of “intergenerational and intragenerational equity”, the principle of “sustainable development” was articulated by the World Commission on Environment and Development in its 1987 report, “Our Common Future”. This “Brundtland Report” defined “sustainable development” as development that “meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” It contains two key concepts: the concept of needs, in particular the essential needs of the present generation, and the idea of limits imposed by the state of technology and social organisation on the environment’s ability to meet present and future needs.⁸³

It identified critical objectives for environment and development policies reflected in the concept of sustainable development. A decade later, in the *Gabcikovo-Nagymaros* case decided by the International Court of Justice in 1997⁸⁴, Judge Weeramantry articulated “sustainable development” as “a principle mediating between development and environmental protection” in a synthesis that serves human well-being. Although the Indian executive has articulated “development”, and the “right to development” as a HRJ both in the domestic and international context, this articulation has been modulated through the

⁸² UN General Assembly, *Declaration on the Right to Development*, UN Doc A/RES/41/128 (4 December 1986). On the classification of the RtD as a “third generation” right, see Karel Vasak, ‘A 30-Year Struggle’ (1977) UNESCO Courier 29; see also Philip Alston (ed.), *Peoples’ Rights* (Oxford University Press, 2001).

⁸³ World Commission on Environment and Development, *Our Common Future* (Oxford University Press, 1987) (the “Brundtland Report”), ch. 2, p. 43. The report was commissioned by the UN General Assembly in Resolution 38/161 (1983).

⁸⁴ Case Concerning the *Gabcikovo-Nagymaros Project (Hungary v. Slovakia)*, ICJ Reports 1997, p. 7, Separate Opinion of Vice-President Weeramantry, p. 88.

use of the principle of “sustainable development” in both contexts, for instance in the Indian government’s articulation of the “right to sustainable development” to oppose trade restrictions imposed by the US in the *Shrimp/Turtle* case before the WTO Appellate Body.⁸⁵ In the domestic context, this can be seen in the way that the judiciary mediates conflicts between the government and individuals with respect to land acquisition for, and environmental impacts of, development projects that come up in the form of constitutional disputes before the Supreme Court of India and High Courts.

Since Judge Weeramantry’s opinion in the *Gabcikov-Nagyamoros* case, other cases have sought to give effect to the concept, including the *Iron Rhine* arbitration⁸⁶ and the ICJ decision in *Pulp Mills*.⁸⁷ The international law of sustainable development encompasses but is not limited to international environmental law; it also includes the social and economic dimension of development, the participatory role of major groups, and financial and other means of implementation.⁸⁸

Subsequent international jurisprudence has continued to invoke “sustainable development” as an interpretive tool. In *Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay* (2010), the ICJ reaffirmed the obligation to integrate environmental protection into developmental planning, recognizing a due diligence obligation to conduct environmental impact assessments for projects with potential transboundary harm. The Seabed Disputes Chamber of ITLOS, in its 2011 *Advisory Opinion on Responsibilities and Obligations of States*,⁸⁹ similarly grounded due diligence obligations in sustainable development principles.

⁸⁵ On the *Shrimp/Turtle* case, see WTO Appellate Body Report, *United States — Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products*, WT/DS58/AB/R, adopted 6 November 1998, para. 129 (where India, as a complaining party, invoked sustainable development in its submissions).

⁸⁶ *Award in the Arbitration regarding the Iron Rhine (“IJzeren Rijn”)* (*Belgium v. Netherlands*), Permanent Court of Arbitration, Award of 24 May 2005, XXVII RIAA 35 (2005).

⁸⁷ *Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay)*, Judgment, I.C.J. Reports 2010, p. 14. ISSN 0074-4441; ISBN 978-92-1-071089-3.

⁸⁸ International Law Association (ILA), *New Delhi Declaration of Principles of International Law Relating to Sustainable Development*, Resolution 3/2002, 70th ILA Conference, New Delhi, 2–6 April 2002, reprinted in (2002) *2 International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics* 211, preamble para. 3.

⁸⁹ *Responsibilities and Obligations of States Sponsoring Persons and Entities with Respect to Activities in the Area*, ITLOS Seabed Disputes Chamber — Advisory Opinion (1 February 2011).

A Value-Based Realism meets Human Rights Justifications through Equality and Interdependency

The mechanism in our project that we have identified as making it possible to bridge the universality of freedom and equality with the recognition of a value-based realism that is forged out of its place and historicity, shapes not only what is possible but also the perception of the universal. This without breaking down into a pluralist framework where rights themselves become contextual. We still insist that a universal approach to human rights is the foundation for multilateralism but the realities of a multipolar World Order demand methods and instruments for maintaining contextual flexibility or, as Stubb argues, a value-based realism. This is where we have identified a conceptual development. We found when examining our place-based empirical data that one “argumental instrument” kept re-appearing throughout our work at the tension points between what one can say is multilateralism and multipolarity. This is the concept we call “related notions.” Related notions is built on how we identify through our place-based approach how the State finds ways of managing the relation between a norm-rule based regime and a State and geopolitical- interests.

Related Notions

The following section is based on Chiara Tea Antoniazzi and Caterina Milo’s Report on “*Related Notions*”, last updated December 2025

The development of the concept of “related notions” has stemmed from the finding that, in the area of climate change especially, States often do not rely on human rights justifications in the strict sense i.e. by quoting a specific human right, but they have recourse to notions that are connected to human rights. Some of these notions are more closely related to the idea of the protection of rights of individuals and groups (e.g., consumers’ interests or

intergenerational equity), while others are more easily located in the sphere of public/State interest (e.g., security in the area of migration). Many can be placed in the middle of this spectrum – such as “development”, which can be conceived as the object of both a State interest and an individual or group right; or the “protection of health”. More generally, “related notions” appear to blur the lines between the protection of the public interest and the protection of the rights of others and therefore constitute a phenomenon worthy of examination.

Examples have been given above regarding the use of related notions by defendant States in litigation contexts, but related notions also recur in legislative acts, including those of the EU (an examination of which is detailed in Deliverable 7.7).

Whereas it is difficult to identify a single or even main reason for this pattern (and the empirical legal approach utilized for the HRJust project is arguably not entirely appropriate to such an effort), context does appear to play a role – e.g., the fact that the WTO Dispute Settlement Body and investment arbitration tribunals do not - as such - adjudicate on the basis of human rights instruments. Project findings from areas other than climate further suggest that some national actors might not be familiar with the use of human rights language in certain contexts thereby resorting to more well-known related notions (e.g., the protection of health). Nevertheless, it appears that not all uses can be explained on the basis of contextual constraints or lack of knowledge. Accordingly, it can be hypothesized that related notions are used strategically to rely on the legitimacy connected to human rights and human rights-related arguments, while potentially circumventing the obligations connected to human rights in the strict sense and maintaining more leeway in a proportionality test. While uses of related notions vary in their forms, contexts and frequency, they are notable as an occurrence that is less visible than the use of human rights justifications but can be a prelude to, or in some way be connected to them.

EU and Human Rights Justifications

This is a short summary: for an extensive report on EU, see D7.7

The EU is not a national actor, so the questions need be tailored somewhat, depending on whether it is an EU Member State raising the claim, or an individual. For an EU Member, several avenues are available. First is initiating an action before the CJEU: Under Article 263 TFEU, a Member State can bring an action for annulment against an EU act believed to breach human rights. The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) has the competence to review the legality of EU acts, including the compatibility with fundamental rights, which are recognized as general principles of EU law and further enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU. Second is an action for damages: Article 268 in conjunction with Article 340 TFEU allows for claims of damages against the EU for unlawful conduct leading to a violation of rights. Complaints can be filed with the European Ombudsman or the European Commission. Recourse to the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) may be available where a human rights breach implicates the European Convention on Human Rights and domestic remedies are exhausted, individuals (and potentially states) can seek review by the ECtHR, even when the underlying law is of EU origin.

An individual has basically the same array of options: Action for Annulment (Article 263(4) TFEU), Action for Damages (Articles 268 and 340 TFEU), Failure to Act (Article 265 TFEU), and Preliminary Ruling via National Courts (Article 267 TFEU). An individual can also resort to the European Ombudsman and the European Commission. Claims can also be made to the ECtHR if an EU Member State, acting within the scope of EU law, violates rights under the European Convention on Human Rights—after exhausting domestic remedies. However, the EU itself is not a party to the Convention, so challenges must be directed at member states, not EU institutions directly.

Most of these avenues are ex-ante. Post-ante would be for the Member State to work through the political system, and for individuals to lobby.

What role has EU in comparison between internal to EU and external to EU

This section summarizes the report, “A Normative Core for a Geopolitical Europe: Policy Recommendation on Human Rights in European Union External Action”, by Sari Kouvo

Human rights are at the heart of the European project and enshrined in the treaties governing the European Union, informing the social contract between Member States and citizens, as well as between EU institutions and the European public. At the global stage, promotion and respect for human rights has been an integral part of EU’s multilateral and bilateral engagements.

Movements challenging basic human rights norms, including those of equality, non-discrimination and the Rule of Law are developing their foothold in democracies inside and outside Europe and autocracies are on the rise. HRJust is showing that international and regional human rights regimes and human rights defenders are ill-equipped to deal with situations where human rights are distorted to serve governance needs, which has significant implications for how EU can continue to secure a space for human rights across EU policy at a time when more flexible approaches are required, reflecting that human rights do not exist in a vacuum but often in competition with competing interests. Or as noted by Alexei Jones, the new framing includes a “...fundamental strategic dilemma: how to reconcile the pursuit of short-term geopolitical and economic interests with the EU’s long-

standing, treaty-based commitment to sustainable development, human rights and democratic governance”.⁹⁰

It is likely that the fourth Human Rights Action Plan for 2028 will be aligned with EU’s Multiannual Financial Framework 2028-2034 (MFF), negotiations on which are currently ongoing, leaving uncertainty about direction and funds available. It appears clear that EU will commit considerably more resources on security and defense and have to address rising concerns from Member States and EU citizens about a range of socio-economic issues. EU has proposed a restructured budget that promotes greater flexibility, with the new “Global” heading, absorbing previously standalone programmes for human rights, Civil Society and global public goods. The draft MFF shared by the European Commission suggests there will be leaner and less specific commitments on human rights. Whilst the proposed overall budget for external action is considerably higher than in the previous budget, negotiations are at early stages and some push-back from some Member States is anticipated. Ensuring budget for human rights will be challenging in already-stretched budgets, and in competition with other themes, with possibly less transparency if specific funding targets are abolished. These pressures challenge EU’s ability fully to achieve its role in upholding and promoting human rights, continuing support to established partnerships, including with human rights defenders, and building new partnerships to defend human rights and international law.

Comparing the general and the particular

It is important to stress here the limitations of the study, and we suggest that further research be made on this correlation between interdependency and the use of HRJs to expand and enhance human rights, in contrast to when HRJs are used to close off the

⁹⁰ ECDPM Briefing note no 198, A companion guide to the Global Europe instrument proposal, Alexei Jones, July 2025

international and instead focus on the national. At that point, HRJs are not part of building and sustaining the multilateral system but instead are drawing legitimacy and authority from the international context to support a national agenda built on domestic self-sufficiency where the international is seen as a threat instead of as a resource.

In this Deliverable and in our project, we have identified areas worthy of further research such as how generalizable our findings on HRJs at the nexus between multilateralism and multipolarity might be. If the relationship we have found between multilateralism and multipolarity especially when it comes to the treatment of migrants within nations goes beyond migration. Similarly, we have found a connection between HRJs and a transition from individual rights to collective rights when it comes to migrants and crime-fighting, and when it comes to the right to health in the aftermath of Covid-19. We did not find any such correlation with climate. This might depend on the fact that the focus was on litigation (including investment- and trade-related litigation). It might be more prevalent if the research had included a more in-depth examination of legislation.

What we also have found but would like to expand and to further legal research on is the distinction between the legislative and the adjudicative legal systems within national jurisdictions. The constitutional design seem to be of high importance for how HRJs will be both regulated and evolving in its relation to a shifting global order. For now, it seems as if the legal systems that allows for Courts to check the legislator might also be better suited to manage bad faith use of HRJs and that systems with weak Courts will be more vulnerable for HRJs to become populist instruments turned into law. A more systemic constitutional comparative study would be needed for a general conclusion to be made.

One finding we have made, and it is of importance, that is that when the State uses HRJs to infringe on already existing individual rights a doctrine for safeguarding the rights of the individual subjected to the HRJs must be developed. A form of minority protection scrutiny to avoid that human rights themselves become the hiding place for discrimination to be legitimized and justified.

Examination of the Topics of Investigation

Are human rights justifications (HRJs) undermining the credibility and legitimacy of the human rights regime itself?

Our work has demonstrated the existence and impacts of HRJs - occasions when human rights are used by the State as a tool of governance, rather than for the purpose for which the human rights regime was originally created, namely as a protection for the individual against the power of the State. HRJs turn the human rights regime itself from being a regime holding the State accountable on behalf of the individual rights-holding subject, to being an instrument of governance on behalf of the State. We cannot point to concrete data that shows that the use of Human Rights Justifications even in bad faith, severely diminishes the legitimacy of the human rights regime, although this was one of the presumptions we initially held when investigating this topic. This does not mean that HRJs used in bad faith might not have a negative effect on the legitimacy of the human rights regime as such, it is just that our results do not demonstrate this. Instead, what we found is that the use of HRJs in bad faith affects the legitimacy of the State's decisions and actions. This is clear in the Swedish case, where our findings suggest that of the five countries studied, Sweden is the country that is the most frequent user of HRJs in bad faith. The implications of this are clear: measures adopted by the government - despite not listening to critique, challenge or opposition, including when it is not feasible for Civil Society to oppose a HRJ –still have legal force, but these measures are not necessarily accepted as “good” law by Human Rights defenders and Civil Society.

We have found that among the most serious effects of the States' use of HRJs is that the nature and scale of the processes and resource requirements for the effective and timely critique of human rights justifications used in bad faith risk detract resources from Civil Society, that now must be used to address HRJs used in bad faith. The intensity of resources required to enable Civil Society to rebut HRJs risk undermine its ability to hold the State

accountable for its actions when the State uses HRJs. Further, even though HRJs involve the State explaining, justifying or defending its actions, the use of HRJs does not seem to bring any added legitimacy to decisions and actions of the State. Instead, it seems that there is a legitimacy cost to the decisions and actions conducted by the State when using HRJs because, in liberal democracies, the State is dependent for its legitimacy on having been scrutinized and on its actions holding up under the scrutiny of Civil Society. When Civil Society is unable to conduct this function because it lacks the advanced legal skills and legal resources needed for engaging with HRJs used in bad faith by States, it therefore seems to of itself weaken the legitimacy of the decisions and actions of the State.

In short, the effect is that the critique gets muted, and because it has not been taken into account, it does not bring greater legitimacy to the decisions and actions of the State. It is still a loss for human rights when HRJs are used to infringe on other rights in bad faith because a law is a law, and it will still have the force of law – even when adopted under the use of a HRJs in bad faith, and even if the law will not carry much legitimacy because it was adopted without proper accountability of the State.

Are human rights justifications being more likely to be used at moments of crisis?

We found that HRJs are more likely to be used after the crisis has normalized actions and decisions of the State that, before the crisis, would not have been accepted by the public. HRJs seems to be more in use in the transition from normalization to institutionalization.

We have also found that there are specific moments when the State and Civil Society might be more vulnerable when a State uses HRJs – and this is in the moment after the Crisis – not as we had originally postulated, during an ongoing crisis – it is instead after the immediate crisis has dissipated that the State is more likely and Civil Society is more vulnerable, to the use of HRJs. The risk of function creep, to use the limitations upon individual rights with the help of HRJs when the “new normal” generated by the Crisis now passed, is used for its institutionalization. The risk with the institutionalization of a limitation or infringement of a

right justified first by the crisis and second by a HRJ is that it will be used once institutionalized for other purposes no longer connected to the original crisis.

Are there significant and important gaps in human rights regulations?

We have identified two significant gaps in human rights regulations.

First, we found that the role of the liberal democratic State in supporting and enabling the human rights regime is under examined and that it is here in large part where there is a gap in regulation. There is no substitute for an active and committed liberal democratic State – neither in the honest and good faith use of human rights both as positive obligations and as compliance, but also as honest and good faith use of HRJs.

What we have found is that when it comes to being an indispensable partner together with Civil Society in the advancement and implementation of human rights. Civil Society will not be able to replace the responsibility of the State in this.

Second, we found on a more legal technical note, a significant gap in the human rights regulations when States use HRJs in bad faith is when this takes place within the legislative phase and when there is no effective form of judicial ex-ante review or as in the case of Sweden not ex-post effective review either. This means that when the State decides to use a HRJ from a human rights treaty without a legally binding authorized Court, there is little protection against the use of HRJs in the legislative phase.

Is there a lack of theoretical understanding of the implications and uncertainties about the role and response of global actors like EU when States use human rights justifications?

With regard to the EU, we have found that EU is an indispensable human rights actor on the international stage – because no other organization has the power and the political flexibility to replace the role of the EU as is clearly shown with the examples of Taiwan and Ukraine,

and to also to some extent with India. It seems as if EU does not have an option to withdraw and retreat from its international multilateral human rights commitment, because no other international – inter-State organization has the capacity like EU to be a geopolitical actor in defense of multilateralism through a platform of shared values and equality. It is noted that EU itself can and does use HRJs, for instance with regard to Ukraine, which enables EU to promote multilateralism, and which have had real important value to the Ukraine legal community and culture.

Recommendations and suggestions for further examination

Recommendation 1: Horizon as a multilateral diplomatic instrument

The first finding we have made is directed to the EU Commission and Horizon and concerns the treatment of partners who are not EU Member States. We have found that after the post-Cold War era, multilateralism starts with the principles of equality and respect between the EU based and the Third country beneficiaries, including Ukraine which is a State on the verge of the EU. Our project is unique in that Taiwan and Indian beneficiaries are full equal partners in the project. The fact that they have been equal partners funded by the EU Commission has made it possible for especially our Taiwan partners to serve a more effect role also within Taiwan in relation to Civil Society and public authorities such as the Constitutional Court, the Universities and also the EEAS. It is not possible to overestimate how important it has been for the establishing of connections and relations between Taiwanese Civil Society and Public Actors with for example the Swedish and European counter parts, that the three beneficiaries from Taiwan are equal and funded project partners in relation to the EU Commission and in relation to the Consortium. In fact, we believe that successful creation of networks between countries and EU would not have been possible had Taiwan's researchers not been equal partners to EU member state partners.

It is only by making our Taiwan and Indian partners, and we hope in the future our Ukraine researchers, full and equal beneficiaries within the project, that they themselves have had the legitimacy and not just the resources to engage fully with the Civil Society and Public Authorities required to fully understand how HRJs are linked to the human rights regimes themselves. How this is done depends on the specific history and context of each place, which could only be fully assessed through close collaboration with Civil Society and national public authorities.

Recommendation 2: Educate Civil Society to be observant that it is after the immediate crisis has passed that the risk of function creep is higher

The second finding, It is key to develop an increased focus and awareness among human rights organizations of the implications of HRJs, particularly when the crisis that led to the original HRJ has passed and society has got used to what was originally described as temporary measures and States desire to use HRJs to make these changes permanent including extending them to other area through function creeps.

Recommendation 3: To expand the capacity for human rights to serve as a comparative matrix for Civil Society when holding the State accountable

The third finding is about the importance of safeguarding human rights as both a comparative system and as a new function as the mediator of the relationship between multilateralism and multipolarity. When used appropriately, the development of HRJs can create an interdependency between Civil Society, national, regional and international instruments which supports multilateralism in its relation to multipolarity by establishing a dignified relationship of equality. However, when HRJs are used to achieve independency between the different levels, human rights

justifications will strengthen multipolarity and lose the meaning of human rights as the foundation of a shared value-based realism.

Recommendation 4: To reform the Horizon reporting system to protect researchers and human rights defenders at risk

The fourth finding is that there is a gap in Horizon reporting process when it comes to researchers and human rights defenders, and EU Horizon ought to create a “safe” or secure reporting system in addition to SyGMA for those at risk of punitive consequences from their own governments when they conduct research within a Horizon project or participate in human rights and democracy promoting activities conducted through Horizon research Civil Society engagements. Either there should be a system besides SyGMA or there should be a function within SyGMA that takes the safety of the researchers and participants into account when reporting research and activities from a Horizon project to the EU Commission.